

Magic Squares of Order 10 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025

Inder J. Taneja¹

The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=15710>

This work is without use of any kind of programming language

Abstract

*This work brings **dates and days of the year**, 2025 in terms of magic squares of order 10 for the month **June, 2025**. Six different types of magic squares of order 10 are considered. Most of them are based on **cornered, single digit bordered and double digits bordered** magic squares. In all the case the respective **magic rectangles** are of equal sums. All the examples represents in two different ways the **dates**, while **days of the year** in all case are represented by **sum of magic squares**. For same kind of work for the orders 3 to 9 refer author's work [31, 32, 33].*

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012).
E-mail: ijaneja@gmail.com; **Web-sites:** <http://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com>; <http://numbers-magic.com>;
Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Magic Squares of Order 10	3
2.1	Reduced Entries: Magic Squares of Order 10	5
3	Reduced Entries Magic Squares: Days and Dates of the Year 2025	12
3.1	June - 2025	12
4	Author’s Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers	57

1 Introduction

In the previous papers the author [31, 32, 33] worked in representing **days** and **dates** of the year 2025 for the magic squares of orders 3 to 9. Let’s call this kind of work as **reduced or less entries** magic squares. A short idea of this kind of representations for orders 3 to 5 can be seen in F. Gaspalou web-site [4], where the representations are in terms of magic sums. This work brings the results in general forms, where we have used **magic sum**, S. In all the cases, the magic sum represents **days of the year** and in **dates** are represented by few of entries. The entries are non sequential positive or negative numbers. For more details refer author’s work [31, 32, 33].

This work brings **dates** and **days** of the year 2025 in terms of magic squares of order 10 for the months of **May to December, 2025**. It is based on **reduced entries** magic squares of order 10. In this work we have considered six types of **reduced entries** magic squares of order 10. Even though there are more five types not considered here as they give **semi-magic** squares results. The six types magic squares of order 10 with **reduced entries** are based on **single digits bordered, double digits bordered** and **cornered** magic squares.

2 Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are three examples of magic squares of order 10.

Example 2.1. *Let's consider a magic square of order 10*

mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/										505
69	87	8	27	10	99	72	95	25	13	505	
14	32	93	74	91	2	29	6	88	76	505	
85	16	49	60	61	38	33	62	24	77	505	
84	17	68	59	47	35	52	42	18	83	505	
90	11	65	41	34	63	64	36	3	98	505	
23	78	39	53	43	54	48	66	96	5	505	
12	89	45	46	67	55	50	40	71	30	505	
79	22	37	44	51	58	56	57	4	97	505	
21	73	75	86	70	1	9	81	82	7	505	
28	80	26	15	31	100	92	20	94	19	505	
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

It is a double digits bordered magic squares where the magic rectangles of order 2×4 are of equal sums.

Example 2.2. *Let's consider a magic square of order 10*

mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/									505
49	54	43	56	61	40	31	70	18	83	505
44	55	50	53	41	60	19	82	5	96	505
58	45	52	47	59	42	72	29	94	7	505
51	48	57	46	67	34	27	74	99	2	505
36	35	62	68	38	64	25	76	95	6	505
65	66	39	33	37	63	71	30	10	91	505
28	26	80	69	24	79	78	20	88	13	505
73	75	21	32	77	22	81	23	8	93	505
15	84	12	90	9	98	97	85	1	14	505
86	17	89	11	92	3	4	16	87	100	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

It is a **cornered** magic squares, where in each case the magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 are of equal sums. It contains magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8. In the left upper corner there is a magic square of order 4.

Example 2.3. Let's consider a magic square of order 10

mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/									505
91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92	505
13	26	20	80	82	69	31	71	25	88	505
89	23	64	62	35	68	36	38	78	12	505
11	24	34	49	54	43	56	67	77	90	505
96	29	40	44	55	50	53	61	72	5	505
1	79	42	58	45	52	47	59	22	100	505
93	74	60	51	48	57	46	41	27	8	505
7	73	63	39	66	33	65	37	28	94	505
95	76	81	21	19	32	70	30	75	6	505
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

It is a well known **single digits bordered** magic square. It also contains magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8.

2.1 Reduced Entries: Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are six magic squares of order 10 with **reduced entries**. These are constructed based on examples 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3.

Example 2.4. Let's consider following *cornered* magic squares of order 10 with reduced entries:

$2*(T-S)/2-A35-A20-A41$	$2*A41+A35+A34+A20-A21-2*A28-3*T/2+5*S/2-A27$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$3*(T-S)/2-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19$	A19	$A21+2*A28-A20+A27-A41-A34$	A20
A27	A28	$(T-S)/2-A15$	$(T-S)/2-A16$	$(T-S)/2-A17$	$(T-S)/2-A18$	$A15+A16+A17+A18+A19-2*(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A19$	$3*S/2-A21-T/2-A27-A28$	A21
$3*(T-S)/2-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	$A22+A23+A24+A25+A26-2*(T-S)/2$	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	S-M-A10	A10	$(T-S)/2-A29$	A29
A22	$(T-S)/2-A22$	A6	A4	A5	$M-A4-A5-A6$	$A10+A11+A12-S+M$	$2*S-2*M-A10-A11-A12$	$(T-S)/2-A30$	A30
A23	$(T-S)/2-A23$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	S-M-A11	A11	$A29+A30+A31+A32+A33-T+S$	$3*(T-S)/2-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33$
A24	$(T-S)/2-A24$	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	S-M-A12	A12	$(T-S)/2-A31$	A31
A25	$(T-S)/2-A25$	S-M-A8	$2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M$	$2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S$	S-M-A9	$(1/2)*(S-M)$	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A32$	A32
A26	$(T-S)/2-A26$	A8	$A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S$	$3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M$	A9	$(5*M-3*S)*(1/2)$	$(S-M)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A33$	A33
$5*S/2-3*T/2+A35+A20-A27$	$3*T/2-5*S/2-A20+A27+A28-A41+A21$	$(T-S)/2-A36$	$A36+A37+A38+A39+A40-T+S$	$(T-S)/2-A37$	$(T-S)/2-A38$	$(T-S)/2-A39$	$(T-S)/2-A40$	$A41+A20-A28$	$3*S/2-A35-T/2-A20-A21$
A41	$3*S/2-T/2-A41-A35-A34$	A36	$3*(T-S)/2-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	A37	A38	A39	A40	A34	A35

It is a *cornered* magic square where there are two equal sums magic rectangle of order 2×8 . In the left upper corner there is a *double digits bordered* magic square of order 8. It contains a *magic square* of order 4, and 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 . In this example, M, S and T represents *magic squares* of orders 4, 6 and 10 respectively.

Example 2.5. Let's consider following *cornered* magic squares of order 10 with reduced entries:

A18	A19	$2*A25-A15-A16-A17$	A15	a16	a17	$T+A18-A19-4*A25+A23$	$2*A25-A23-2*A18$	L-T-A28	A28
$2*A13+A24+A14+2*A18-2*A25-A19$	$2*A25-2*A18-A13$	$A15+A16+A17-A25$	A25-A15	A25-A16	A25-A17	$2*A25-A23-A13-A24-A18+A19$	$T-4*A25+A18+A23-A14$	L-T-A29	A29
$2*A25-A7-A8-A9$	$A7+A8+A9-A25$	A1	$A4+T-2*A25-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$A10+A11+A12-A25$	$2*A25-A10-A11-A12$	$A28+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+3*T-3*L$	$4*L-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-4*T$
A7	A25-A7	A6	A4	A5	$T-2*A25-A4-A5-A6$	A25-A10	A10	L-T-A30	A30
A8	A25-A8	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$T-2*A25-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	A25-A11	A11	L-T-A31	A31
A9	A25-A9	$T-2*A25-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	A25-A12	A12	L-T-A32	A32
$T-2*A13-A14+A19-3*A18-A23-A24$	$A23+3*A18+A24-A19+A13-2*A25$	$A20+A21+A22-A25$	A25-A20	A25-A21	A25-A22	A13	A14	L-T-A33	A33
A23	$T-A23-A18-2*A25-A24$	$2*A25-A20-A21-A22$	A20	a21	a22	A24	A18	L-T-A34	A34
L-T-A35	$T-A1+A29-A28+A11+A21+A22+2*A20-6*A25-A35+2*A10+A12-3*A4$	$T+A1-A29+A28-A11-A21-A22-2*A20+6*A25+2*A35-2*A10-A12-2*L+3*A4+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40$	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	$(L-T)/2$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
A35	$A1-A29+A28-A11-A21-A22-2*A20+6*A25+A35-2*T-2*A10-A12+L+3*A4$	$3*L-2*T-A1+A29-A28+A11+A21+A22+2*A20-6*A25-2*A35+2*A10+A12-3*A4-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	$(L-T)/2$

It is a *cornered* magic square of order 10, where the respective *magic rectangles* are of equal sums. These are of orders 2×8 . In the left upper there is a *double digits* magic square of order 8, where the respective *magic rectangles* are of equal sums. These are of orders 2×4 . It also contains a *magic square* of order 4 in the middle. In this example, T and L represents *magic sums* of orders 8 and 10 respectively. The magic sum of order 4 is represented by $T - 2 \times A25$.

Example 2.6. Let's consider following *cornered* magic squares of order 10 with reduced entries:

A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	T-S-A17	A17	L-T-A23	A23
A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10+A11+A12-S+M	2*S-2*M-A10-A11-A12	T-4*S-A17+A1+2*M+2*A9+2*A8+3*A4	A17-A1-2*M+3*S-2*A9-2*A8-3*A4	L-T-A24	A24
A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	S-M-A11	A11	2*A17+A19+A20-A1-2*M+5*S-2*T-2*A9-2*A8-3*A4+A18	3*T-6*S-A19-A20-2*A17+A1+2*M+2*A9+2*A8+3*A4-A18	A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28+A29+3*T-3*L	4*L-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-4*T
M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	S-M-A12	A12	T-S-A18	A18	L-T-A25	A25
S-M-A8	2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M	2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	(5*M-3*S)/2	T-S-A19	A19	L-T-A26	A26
A8	A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S	3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M	A9	(5*M-3*S)/2	(S-M)/2	T-S-A20	A20	L-T-A27	A27
T+2*S-3*M-2*A9-2*A8	2*A10+2*A12-M+2*S-2*A9-2*A8	A16-4*S+4*M-T+4*A9+4*A8+A15+A14-2*A12-2*A10	T-S-A14	T-S-A15	T-S-A16	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2	L-T-A28	A28
2*A9+2*A8-3*S+3*M	2*A9+2*A8+M+T-3*S-2*A10-2*A12	2*T+3*S-A15-A14-4*M-4*A9-4*A8+2*A12+2*A10-A16	A14	A15	A16	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2	L-T-A29	A29
2*L+4*T+A1-A30+2*A12+2*A10+A23-A24-2*A8-A16-A15-2*A14-2*A18-A20-A19-2*A17-2*A9+3*M+3*A4-8*S	L-T-A30	2*A30-2*T-2*A12-2*A10-A23+A24+2*A8+A16+A15+2*A14-4*L+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31+2*A18+A20+A19+2*A17+2*A9-3*M-3*A4-A1+8*S	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	(L-T)/2	(9*T-7*L)/2
A30-5*T-2*A12-2*A10-A23+A24+2*A8+A16+A15+2*A14-L+2*A18+A20+A19+2*A17+2*A9-3*M-3*A4+8*S-A1	A30	T+2*A12+2*A10+A23-A24-2*A8-A16-A15-2*A14+5*L-A35-A34-A33-A32-A31-2*A18-A20-A19-2*A17-2*A9+3*M+3*A4+A1-8*S-2*A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	(9*T-7*L)/2	(L-T)/2

It is a *cornered* magic square of order 10, where the respective *magic rectangles* are of equal sums. These are of orders 2×8 , 2×6 and 2×6 . It contains magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8. In this example, M, S, T and L represents *magic squares* of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 respectively.

Example 2.7. Let's consider following *cornered* magic squares of order 10 with reduced entries:

$4*S-6*M+A12$	$S+2*A13+2*A14-4*A12-M$	$2*A12+9*M-6*S-A13-A14$	$S-A13-M$	$S-A14-M$	$A12$	$T-S-A16$	$A16$	$L-T-A25$	$A25$
$4*M-3*S+A9+A10+A11$	$A1$	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	$A3$	$4*S-A9-A10-A11-5*M$	$T-S-A16-A1-A13-A9-A14+2*A12-7*S-3*A4+10*M$	$A16+A1+A13+A9+A14-2*A12+7*S+3*A4-10*M$	$3*T-3*L+A25+A26+A27+A28+A29+A30+A3$	$4*L-4*T-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31$
$S-A9-M$	$A6$	$A4$	$A5$	$M-A4-A5-A6$	$A9$	$2*A16+A18+A19+A1-2*T+9*S+A13+A9+A14-2*A12+3*A4-10*M+A17$	$3*T-10*S-A18-A19-2*A16-A1-A13-A9-A14+2*A12-3*A4+10*M-A17$	$L-T-A26$	$A26$
$S-A10-M$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	$A10$	$T-S-A17$	$A17$	$L-T-A27$	$A27$
$S-A11-M$	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	$A2$	$A11$	$T-S-A18$	$A18$	$L-T-A28$	$A28$
$5*M-A12-3*S$	$4*A12-2*A13-2*A14$	$7*S+A13+A14-2*A12-10*M$	$A13$	$A14$	$5*M-A12-3*S$	$T-S-A19$	$A19$	$L-T-A29$	$A29$
$T-S+A13+A9+A14-2*A12+2*A1+7*S+6*A4-11*M$	$8*S+A13+A9+A14-2*A12+2*A1+6*A4-11*M$	$A21+A20+A22-T-2*A13-2*A9-2*A14+4*A12-4*A1-14*S-12*A4+22*M$	$T-S-A20$	$T-S-A21$	$T-S-A22$	$(T-S)/2$	$(7*S-5*T)/2$	$L-T-A30$	$A30$
$11*M-A13-A9-A14+2*A12-2*A1-7*S-6*A4$	$T-9*S-A13-A9-A14+2*A12-2*A1-6*A4+11*M$	$2*T+13*S+2*A13+2*A9+2*A14-4*A12+4*A1+12*A4-22*M-A21-A20-A22$	$A20$	$A21$	$A22$	$(7*S-5*T)/2$	$(T-S)/2$	$L-T-A31$	$A31$
$L-T-A32$	$4*L+2*A17+A19+A18+2*A16+12*M-9*A4+2*A12-3*A1-S-A13-A9-2*A14-A11+A21+2*A20+A22-A32-10*T-2*A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31$	$2*A32+12*T+2*A25+A26+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31-6*L+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33-2*A17-A19-A18-2*A16-12*M+9*A4-2*A12+3*A1+S+A13+A9+2*A14+A11-A21-2*A20-A22$	$L-T-A33$	$L-T-A34$	$L-T-A35$	$L-T-A36$	$L-T-A37$	$(L-T)/2$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
$A32$	$A32+9*T+2*A25+A26+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31-3*L-2*A17-A19-A18-2*A16-12*M+9*A4-2*A12+3*A1+S+A13+A9+2*A14+A11-A21-2*A20-A22$	$2*A17+A19+A18+2*A16+12*M-9*A4+2*A12-3*A1-S-A13-A9-2*A14-A11+A21+2*A20+A22-2*A32-13*T-2*A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31+7*L-A37-A36-A35-A34-A33$	$A33$	$A34$	$A35$	$A36$	$A37$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	$(L-T)/2$

It is also a *cornered* magic square of order 10, where the *magic rectangles* of order 2×8 are of equal sums. In the left upper corner there is again a *cornered* magic square of order 8 containing *single digits bordered* magic square of order 6. It also contains *equal sums magic rectangles* of order 2×6 and a *magic square* of order 4. In this example also M, S, T and L represents *magic squares* of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 respectively.

Example 2.8. Let's consider following *cornered* magic squares of order 10 with reduced entries:

T-S-A17	$2*T+3*S+A19-A14-A20$	T-S-A14	$A18+2*A17-7*T+2*S+A16+A15+2*A14+A21+A22+A24+2*A20+A23$	T-S-A15	T-S-A16	T-S-A18	T-A21-A22-A24-A20-A23-A17-A19	L-T-A32	A32
T-S-A20	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	A20	L-T-A33	A33
T-S-A21	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	$A10+A11+A12-S+M$	$2*S-2*M-A10-A11-A12$	A21	$A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+3*T-3*L$	$4*L-4*T-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38$
T-S-A22	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	S-M-A11	A11	A22	L-T-A34	A34
T-S-A23	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	S-M-A12	A12	A23	L-T-A35	A35
T-S-A24	S-M-A8	$2*S-A8-A1+A33-2*A10-A11-A12-M$	$2*A8+A1+A9-A33+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S$	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	A24	L-T-A36	A36
T-S-A19	A8	$A8+A1-A33+2*A10+A11+A12-S$	$3*S-2*A8-A1-A9+A33-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M$	A9	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	(S-M)/2	A19	L-T-A37	A37
$A17+A19+7*S+A21+A22+A24+A20+A23-6*T$	$A14+A20-T-A19-4*S$	A14	$8*T-A18-2*A17-3*S-A16-A15-2*A14-A21-A22-A24-2*A20-A23$	A15	A16	A18	A17	L-T-A38	A38
$2*L-3*T-A1-A26+5*S-4*M-2*A8+A21-2*A10-2*A12-2*A9+A14+A32$	L-T-A26	$5*T-4*L+2*A26+A1-5*S+4*M+2*A8-A21+2*A10+2*A12+2*A9-A14-A32+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31$	L-T-A27	L-T-A28	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	(L-T)/2	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
$A1+2*T+A26-5*S+4*M+2*A8-L-A21+2*A10+2*A12+2*A9-A14-A32$	A26	$5*L-6*T-2*A26-A1+5*S-4*M-2*A8+A21-2*A10-2*A12-2*A9+A14+A32-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31$	A27	A28	A29	A30	A31	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	(L-T)/2

It is also a *double digits bordered* magic squares where all the four *magic rectangles* of order 2×8 are of equal sums. There is a *bordered* magic square of order 8 containing *cornered* magic squares of order 6. In this case, the *magic rectangles* of order 2×4 are of equal sums. In this example also M, S, T and L represents *magic squares* of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 respectively.

Example 2.9. Let's consider following *cornered* magic squares of order 10 with reduced entries:

T-S-A25	$2*T+3*S+A16-2*A13-A22-2*A12-2*A8-5*M-3*A4-A17-2*A14$	T-S-A22	$A26+2*A25+2*A13-7*T+2*S+A24+A23+2*A22+2*A12+2*A8+5*M+3*A4+A18+A19+A21+2*A17+2*A14+A20$	T-S-A23	T-S-A24	T-S-A26	T-A18-A19-A21-A17-A20-A25-A16	L-T-A29	A29
T-S-A17	S-M-A14	S-A12-M	$2*A11-3*A4-A12-A8+A9+M$	$3*A4-3*S+2*A12+A13+2*A8+A9-A10+2*A14+2*M$	S-A13-M	S-A8-A9-A10-A11-A14	A17	L-T-A30	A30
T-S-A18	S-M-A9	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	A9	A18	$A29+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+3*T-3*L$	$4*L-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-4*T$
T-S-A19	S-M-A10	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10	A19	L-T-A31	A31
T-S-A20	S-M-A11	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	A11	A20	L-T-A32	A32
T-S-A21	S-M-A8	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	A8	A21	L-T-A33	A33
T-S-A16	$A8+A9+A10+A11+A14+5*M-4*S$	A12	$S-2*A11+3*A4+A12+A8-A9-2*M$	$4*S+A11-3*A4-2*A12-A13-2*A8-A10-2*A14-3*M$	A13	A14	A16	L-T-A34	A34
$A25+A16+7*S+A18+A19+A21+A17+A20-6*T$	$A22+2*A12+2*A8+5*M+3*A4+A17+2*A14-T-A16+2*A13-4*S$	A22	$8*T-A26-2*A25-2*A13-3*S-A24-A23-2*A22-2*A12-2*A8-5*M-3*A4-A18-A19-A21-2*A17-2*A14-A20$	A23	A24	A26	A25	L-T-A35	A35
L-T-A36	$A30-A29-A18-A36+T-A12-A22+2*A11+A9-S-A8-6*A4+2*M-A1-A10$	$A29-A30+A18+A38+A37+A40+2*A36+T+A12+A22-2*A11+A39-A9-2*L+S+A8+6*A4-2*M+A1+A10+A41$	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	L-T-A41	(L-T)/2	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
A36	$A29-A30+A18+A36-2*T+A12+A22-2*A11-A9+L+S+A8+6*A4-2*M+A1+A10$	$A30-A29-A18-A38-A37-A40-2*A36-2*T-A12-A22+2*A11-A39+A9+3*L-S-A8-6*A4+2*M-A1-A10-A41$	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	(L-T)/2

It is also a *cornered* magic square of order 10, where the *magic rectangles* of order 2×8 are of equal sums. In the left upper corner there is a *single digit bordered* magic square of order 8 embedded with a magic square of order 4.

The examples given in the next section are based on the Examples 2.4 to 2.9, where the entries are **dates** and magic sum is **day** of the year 2025.

3 Reduced Entries Magic Squares: Days and Dates of the Year 2025

This work brings **dates** and **days of the year**, 2025 in terms of magic squares of order 10. This section is only for the month **June, 2025**. As explained above, here are six types of magic squares of order 10 are considered here. The readers can see the complete work for the months May to December, 2025 at the link <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=15710>.

3.1 June - 2025

■ 152nd Day of the Year - 01.06.2025

1	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									152
-56	54	25	26	27	28	-30	29	19	30	152	
37	38	10	9	8	7	65	6	-59	31	152	
-65	100	01	55	-10	06	10	20	-4	39	152	
32	3	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	-5	40	152	
33	2	1	-13	20	44	9	21	135	-100	152	
34	1	34	-10	17	11	8	22	-6	41	152	
35	0	12	-50	87	11	15	7	-7	42	152	
36	-1	18	80	-57	19	7	15	-8	43	152	
15	48	-71	2205	-12	-13	-14	-1990	43	-59	152	
51	-93	0106	-2170	47	48	49	2025	44	45	152	
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	

1	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									152
28	29	-18	25	26	27	38	-29	-12	38	152	
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	43	-13	39	152	
6	24	01	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	152	
17	13	16	20	25	5	10	20	-14	40	152	
18	12	1	-13	34	44	9	21	-15	41	152	
19	11	48	-10	17	11	8	22	-16	42	152	
-66	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	152	
33	-29	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	152	
-80	-14	2283	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	35	152	
0106	40	-2257	46	47	48	49	2025	35	13	152	
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	

1	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										152
01	65	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	17	33	152		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	6	14	16	34	152		
1	-13	30	44	-1	21	88	-68	102	-52	152		
44	-10	17	11	-2	22	-8	28	15	35	152		
2	-60	97	1	10	32	-9	29	14	36	152		
18	80	-77	19	32	10	-10	30	13	37	152		
6	112	2037	-4	-86	-2005	10	32	12	38	152		
14	-92	-2017	24	0106	2025	32	10	11	39	152		
-2076	10	2231	9	8	7	6	5	25	-73	152		
2126	40	-2181	41	42	43	44	45	-73	25	152		
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152		

1	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										152
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	15	35	152		
71	01	65	-10	06	-51	-46	66	116	-66	152		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	136	-116	14	36	152		
-3	3	-11	28	42	23	-7	27	13	37	152		
-4	42	-12	19	13	24	-8	28	12	38	152		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	11	39	152		
59	121	-87	-10	-11	-12	10	32	10	40	152		
-39	-101	107	30	31	32	32	10	9	41	152		
-56	-130	2339	7	6	5	4	-1975	25	-73	152		
0106	180	-2289	43	44	45	46	2025	-73	25	152		
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152		

1	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										152
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	-12	42	152		
12	01	67	-14	06	0	20	30	-13	43	152		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	225	-195	152		
10	5	-13	28	40	-1	21	32	-14	44	152		
9	42	-14	21	11	-2	22	33	-15	45	152		
8	2	41	-4	1	10	30	34	-16	46	152		
13	18	-21	24	19	30	10	29	-17	47	152		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	-18	48	152		
-70	-76	2296	-7	-8	-9	-1995	-11	15	17	152		
100	0106	-2266	37	38	39	2025	41	17	15	152		
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152		

1	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										152
11	-25	14	171	13	12	10	-80	-13	39	152		
19	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	152		
18	11	01	57	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	152		
17	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	152		
16	9	5	-13	18	40	21	30	-16	42	152		
15	12	32	-14	21	11	18	31	-17	43	152		
20	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	152		
10	71	32	-125	33	34	36	35	-19	45	152		
-20	-79	2454	-180	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	35	152		
46	105	-2428	0206	2025	49	50	51	35	13	152		
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152		

■ 153rd Day of the Year - 02.06.2025

2	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
-54	50	25	26	27	28	-27	29	19	30	153		
37	38	11	10	9	8	63	7	-61	31	153		
-62	98	02	53	-10	06	10	20	-3	39	153		
32	4	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	-4	40	153		
33	3	1	-12	18	44	9	21	133	-97	153		
34	2	32	-10	18	11	8	22	-5	41	153		
35	1	12	-52	89	11	15	6	-6	42	153		
36	0	18	82	-59	19	6	15	-7	43	153		
11	52	-170	2303	-11	-12	-13	-1989	43	-61	153		
51	-95	0206	-2267	47	48	49	2025	44	45	153		
153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153		

2	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										153
28	29	-18	25	26	27	39	-29	-12	38	153		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	44	-13	39	153		
6	24	02	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	153		
17	13	16	20	25	6	10	20	-14	40	153		
18	12	1	-12	34	44	9	21	-15	41	153		
19	11	48	-10	18	11	8	22	-16	42	153		
-65	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	153		
33	-28	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	153		
-180	-114	2483	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	36	153		
0206	140	-2457	46	47	48	49	2025	36	13	153		
153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153		

2	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
02	65	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	17	33	153		
16	20	25	2	43	-23	6	14	16	34	153		
1	-12	30	44	-1	21	88	-68	102	-52	153		
44	-10	18	11	-2	22	-8	28	15	35	153		
2	-60	97	1	10	33	-9	29	14	36	153		
18	80	-77	19	33	10	-10	30	13	37	153		
6	113	2136	-4	-186	-2005	10	33	12	38	153		
14	-93	-2116	24	0206	2025	33	10	11	39	153		
-2174	10	2329	9	8	7	6	5	25	-72	153		
2224	40	-2279	41	42	43	44	45	-72	25	153		
153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153		

2	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										153
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	15	35	153		
72	02	65	-10	06	-52	-44	64	116	-66	153		
-2	16	20	25	2	22	134	-114	14	36	153		
-3	3	-10	28	42	23	-7	27	13	37	153		
-4	42	-12	20	13	24	-8	28	12	38	153		
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	11	39	153		
57	120	-84	-10	-11	-12	10	33	10	40	153		
-37	-100	104	30	31	32	33	10	9	41	153		
-156	-228	2537	7	6	5	4	-1975	25	-72	153		
0206	278	-2487	43	44	45	46	2025	-72	25	153		
153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153		

2	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	-12	42	153		
13	02	56	-14	06	10	20	30	-13	43	153		
12	12	20	25	-7	33	-3	31	225	-195	153		
11	5	-12	17	40	9	21	32	-14	44	153		
10	31	-14	22	11	8	22	33	-15	45	153		
9	12	50	-13	11	15	5	34	-16	46	153		
14	18	-20	43	19	5	15	29	-17	47	153		
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	-18	48	153		
-132	-176	2458	-7	-8	-9	-1995	-11	15	18	153		
162	0206	-2428	37	38	39	2025	41	18	15	153		
153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153		

2	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										153
12	-23	15	164	14	13	11	-79	-13	39	153		
20	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	153		
19	11	02	56	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	153		
18	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	153		
17	9	5	-12	17	40	21	30	-16	42	153		
16	12	31	-14	22	11	18	31	-17	43	153		
21	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	153		
4	70	32	-117	33	34	36	35	-19	45	153		
-20	-79	2454	-180	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	36	153		
46	105	-2428	0206	2025	49	50	51	36	13	153		
153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153		

■ 154th Day of the Year - 03.06.2025

3	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154
-54	51	25	26	27	28	-27	29	19	30	154		
37	38	11	10	9	8	63	7	-60	31	154		
-62	98	03	53	-10	06	10	20	-3	39	154		
32	4	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	-4	40	154		
33	3	1	-11	18	44	9	21	133	-97	154		
34	2	32	-10	19	11	8	22	-5	41	154		
35	1	12	-52	89	11	15	7	-6	42	154		
36	0	18	82	-59	19	7	15	-7	43	154		
12	51	-270	2403	-11	-12	-13	-1989	43	-60	154		
51	-94	0306	-2367	47	48	49	2025	44	45	154		
154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154		

3	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										154
28	29	-18	25	26	27	40	-29	-12	38	154		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	45	-13	39	154		
6	24	03	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	154		
17	13	16	20	25	7	10	20	-14	40	154		
18	12	1	-11	34	44	9	21	-15	41	154		
19	11	48	-10	19	11	8	22	-16	42	154		
-64	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	154		
33	-27	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	154		
-280	-214	2683	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	37	154		
0306	240	-2657	46	47	48	49	2025	37	13	154		
154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154		

3	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154
03	63	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	19	33	154		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	8	12	18	34	154		
1	-11	28	44	-1	21	86	-66	96	-44	154		
42	-10	19	11	-2	22	-8	28	17	35	154		
2	-62	99	1	10	32	-9	29	16	36	154		
18	82	-79	19	32	10	-10	30	15	37	154		
6	112	2237	-4	-286	-2005	10	32	14	38	154		
14	-92	-2217	24	0306	2025	32	10	13	39	154		
-2270	12	2421	11	10	9	8	7	26	-80	154		
2322	40	-2369	41	42	43	44	45	-80	26	154		
154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154		

3	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										154
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	17	35	154		
71	03	63	-10	06	-51	-48	68	110	-58	154		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	138	-118	16	36	154		
-3	3	-9	26	42	23	-7	27	15	37	154		
-4	40	-12	21	13	24	-8	28	14	38	154		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	13	39	154		
63	125	-95	-10	-11	-12	10	32	12	40	154		
-43	-105	115	30	31	32	32	10	11	41	154		
-254	-328	2733	9	8	7	6	-1973	26	-80	154		
0306	380	-2681	43	44	45	46	2025	-80	26	154		
154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154		

3	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	-10	42	154		
12	03	65	-14	06	0	20	30	-11	43	154		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	219	-187	154		
10	5	-11	26	40	-1	21	32	-12	44	154		
9	40	-14	23	11	-2	22	33	-13	45	154		
8	2	39	-2	1	10	30	34	-14	46	154		
13	18	-19	22	19	30	10	29	-15	47	154		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	-16	48	154		
-268	-274	2690	-5	-6	-7	-1993	-9	16	10	154		
300	0306	-2658	37	38	39	2025	41	10	16	154		
154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154		

3	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										154
13	-21	16	157	15	14	12	-78	-13	39	154		
21	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	154		
20	11	03	55	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	154		
19	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	154		
18	9	5	-11	16	40	21	30	-16	42	154		
17	12	30	-14	23	11	18	31	-17	43	154		
22	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	154		
-2	69	32	-109	33	34	36	35	-19	45	154		
-20	-79	2554	-280	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	37	154		
46	105	-2528	0306	2025	49	50	51	37	13	154		
154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154		

■ 155th Day of the Year - 04.06.2025

4	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155
-52	47	25	26	27	28	-24	29	19	30	155		
37	38	12	11	10	9	61	8	-62	31	155		
-59	96	04	51	-10	06	10	20	-2	39	155		
32	5	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	-3	40	155		
33	4	1	-10	16	44	9	21	131	-94	155		
34	3	30	-10	20	11	8	22	-4	41	155		
35	2	12	-54	91	11	15	6	-5	42	155		
36	1	18	84	-61	19	6	15	-6	43	155		
8	55	-369	2501	-10	-11	-12	-1988	43	-62	155		
51	-96	0406	-2464	47	48	49	2025	44	45	155		
155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155		

4	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										155
28	29	-18	25	26	27	41	-29	-12	38	155		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	46	-13	39	155		
6	24	04	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	155		
17	13	16	20	25	8	10	20	-14	40	155		
18	12	1	-10	34	44	9	21	-15	41	155		
19	11	48	-10	20	11	8	22	-16	42	155		
-63	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	155		
33	-26	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	155		
-380	-314	2883	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	38	155		
0406	340	-2857	46	47	48	49	2025	38	13	155		
155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155		

4	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155
04	63	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	19	33	155		
16	20	25	2	43	-23	8	12	18	34	155		
1	-10	28	44	-1	21	86	-66	96	-44	155		
42	-10	20	11	-2	22	-8	28	17	35	155		
2	-62	99	1	10	33	-9	29	16	36	155		
18	82	-79	19	33	10	-10	30	15	37	155		
6	113	2336	-4	-386	-2005	10	33	14	38	155		
14	-93	-2316	24	0406	2025	33	10	13	39	155		
-2368	12	2519	11	10	9	8	7	26	-79	155		
2420	40	-2467	41	42	43	44	45	-79	26	155		
155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155		

4	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										155
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	17	35	155		
72	04	63	-10	06	-52	-46	66	110	-58	155		
-2	16	20	25	2	22	136	-116	16	36	155		
-3	3	-8	26	42	23	-7	27	15	37	155		
-4	40	-12	22	13	24	-8	28	14	38	155		
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	13	39	155		
61	124	-92	-10	-11	-12	10	33	12	40	155		
-41	-104	112	30	31	32	33	10	11	41	155		
-354	-426	2931	9	8	7	6	-1973	26	-79	155		
0406	478	-2879	43	44	45	46	2025	-79	26	155		
155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155		

4	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	-10	42	155		
13	04	64	-14	06	0	20	30	-11	43	155		
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	219	-187	155		
11	5	-10	25	40	-1	21	32	-12	44	155		
10	39	-14	24	11	-2	22	33	-13	45	155		
9	2	38	-1	1	10	30	34	-14	46	155		
14	18	-18	21	19	30	10	29	-15	47	155		
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	-16	48	155		
-370	-374	2892	-5	-6	-7	-1993	-9	16	11	155		
402	0406	-2860	37	38	39	2025	41	11	16	155		
155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155		

4	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										155
14	-19	17	150	16	15	13	-77	-13	39	155		
22	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	155		
21	11	04	54	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	155		
20	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	155		
19	9	5	-10	15	40	21	30	-16	42	155		
18	12	29	-14	24	11	18	31	-17	43	155		
23	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	155		
-8	68	32	-101	33	34	36	35	-19	45	155		
-20	-79	2654	-380	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	38	155		
46	105	-2628	0406	2025	49	50	51	38	13	155		
155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155		

■ 156th Day of the Year - 05.06.2025

5	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
-52	48	025	26	27	208	-24	29	19	30	156		
37	38	12	11	10	9	61	8	-61	31	156		
-59	96	05	51	-10	06	10	20	-2	39	156		
32	5	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	-3	40	156		
33	4	1	-9	16	44	9	21	131	-94	156		
34	3	30	-10	21	11	8	22	-4	41	156		
35	2	12	-54	91	11	15	7	-5	42	156		
36	1	18	84	-61	19	7	15	-6	43	156		
9	54	-469	2601	-10	-11	-12	-1988	43	-61	156		
51	-95	0506	-2564	47	48	49	2025	44	45	156		
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156		

5	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										156
28	29	-18	25	26	27	42	-29	-12	38	156		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	47	-13	39	156		
6	24	05	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	156		
17	13	16	20	25	9	10	20	-14	40	156		
18	12	1	-9	34	44	9	21	-15	41	156		
19	11	48	-10	21	11	8	22	-16	42	156		
-62	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	156		
33	-25	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	156		
-480	-414	3083	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	39	156		
0506	440	-3057	46	47	48	49	2025	39	13	156		
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156		

5	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
05	61	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	21	33	156		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	10	10	20	34	156		
1	-9	26	44	-1	21	84	-64	90	-36	156		
40	-10	21	11	-2	22	-8	28	19	35	156		
2	-64	101	1	10	32	-9	29	18	36	156		
18	84	-81	19	32	10	-10	30	17	37	156		
6	112	2437	-4	-486	-2005	10	32	16	38	156		
14	-92	-2417	24	0506	2025	32	10	15	39	156		
-2464	14	2611	13	12	11	10	9	27	-87	156		
2518	40	-2557	41	42	43	44	45	-87	27	156		
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156		

5	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										156
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	19	35	156		
71	05	61	-10	06	-51	-50	70	104	-50	156		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	140	-120	18	36	156		
-3	3	-7	24	42	23	-7	27	17	37	156		
-4	38	-12	23	13	24	-8	28	16	38	156		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	15	39	156		
67	129	-103	-10	-11	-12	10	32	14	40	156		
-47	-109	123	30	31	32	32	10	13	41	156		
-452	-526	3127	11	10	9	8	-1971	27	-87	156		
0506	580	-3073	43	44	45	46	2025	-87	27	156		
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156		

5	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	-8	42	156		
12	05	63	-14	06	0	20	30	-9	43	156		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	213	-179	156		
10	5	-9	24	40	-1	21	32	-10	44	156		
9	38	-14	25	11	-2	22	33	-11	45	156		
8	2	37	0	1	10	30	34	-12	46	156		
13	18	-17	20	19	30	10	29	-13	47	156		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	-14	48	156		
-466	-472	3084	-3	-4	-5	-1991	-7	17	3	156		
500	0506	-3050	37	38	39	2025	41	3	17	156		
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156		

5	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										156
15	-17	18	143	17	16	14	-76	-13	39	156		
23	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	156		
22	11	05	53	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	156		
21	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	156		
20	9	5	-9	14	40	21	30	-16	42	156		
19	12	28	-14	25	11	18	31	-17	43	156		
24	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	156		
-14	67	32	-93	33	34	36	35	-19	45	156		
-20	-79	2754	-480	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	39	156		
46	105	-2728	0506	2025	49	50	51	39	13	156		
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156		

■ 157th Day of the Year - 06.06.2025

6	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									157
-50	44	025	26	27	208	-21	29	19	30	157	
37	38	13	12	11	10	59	9	-63	31	157	
-56	94	06	49	-10	06	10	20	-1	39	157	
32	6	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	-2	40	157	
33	5	1	-8	14	44	9	21	129	-91	157	
34	4	28	-10	22	11	8	22	-3	41	157	
35	3	12	-56	93	11	15	6	-4	42	157	
36	2	18	86	-63	19	6	15	-5	43	157	
5	58	-568	2699	-9	-10	-11	-1987	43	-63	157	
51	-97	0606	-2661	47	48	49	2025	44	45	157	
157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	

6	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									157
28	29	-18	25	26	27	43	-29	-12	38	157	
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	48	-13	39	157	
6	24	06	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	157	
17	13	16	20	25	10	10	20	-14	40	157	
18	12	1	-8	34	44	9	21	-15	41	157	
19	11	48	-10	22	11	8	22	-16	42	157	
-61	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	157	
33	-24	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	157	
-580	-514	3283	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	40	157	
0606	540	-3257	46	47	48	49	2025	40	13	157	
157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	

6	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									157
06	61	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	21	33	157	
16	20	25	2	43	-23	10	10	20	34	157	
1	-8	26	44	-1	21	84	-64	90	-36	157	
40	-10	22	11	-2	22	-8	28	19	35	157	
2	-64	101	1	10	33	-9	29	18	36	157	
18	84	-81	19	33	10	-10	30	17	37	157	
6	113	2536	-4	-586	-2005	10	33	16	38	157	
14	-93	-2516	24	0606	2025	33	10	15	39	157	
-2562	14	2709	13	12	11	10	9	27	-86	157	
2616	40	-2655	41	42	43	44	45	-86	27	157	
157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	

6	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									157
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	19	35	157	
72	06	61	-10	06	-52	-48	68	104	-50	157	
-2	16	20	25	2	22	138	-118	18	36	157	
-3	3	-6	24	42	23	-7	27	17	37	157	
-4	38	-12	24	13	24	-8	28	16	38	157	
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	15	39	157	
65	128	-100	-10	-11	-12	10	33	14	40	157	
-45	-108	120	30	31	32	33	10	13	41	157	
-552	-624	3325	11	10	9	8	-1971	27	-86	157	
0606	678	-3271	43	44	45	46	2025	-86	27	157	
157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	

6	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										157
42	464	45	-448	44	43	41	-108	-8	42	157		
39	06	52	-14	06	-10	20	24	-9	43	157		
38	12	20	25	-7	53	-43	25	213	-179	157		
37	5	-8	13	40	-11	21	26	-10	44	157		
36	27	-14	26	11	-12	22	27	-11	45	157		
35	-8	6	31	-9	5	35	28	-12	46	157		
-17	18	4	-21	19	35	5	80	-13	47	157		
-87	-401	18	511	19	20	22	21	-14	48	157		
-640	-572	3422	3	2	1	-1991	-89	17	4	157		
674	0606	-3388	31	32	33	2025	123	4	17	157		
157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157		

6	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										157
16	-15	19	136	18	17	15	-75	-13	39	157		
24	6	8	011	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	157		
23	11	06	52	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	157		
22	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	157		
21	9	5	-8	13	40	21	30	-16	42	157		
20	12	27	-14	26	11	18	31	-17	43	157		
25	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	157		
-20	66	32	-85	33	34	36	35	-19	45	157		
-20	-79	2854	-580	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	40	157		
46	105	-2828	0606	2025	49	50	51	40	13	157		
157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157		

■ 158th Day of the Year - 07.06.2025

7	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										158
-50	45	25	26	27	28	-21	29	19	30	158		
37	38	13	12	11	10	59	9	-62	31	158		
-56	94	07	49	-10	06	10	20	-1	39	158		
32	6	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	-2	40	158		
33	5	1	-7	14	44	9	21	129	-91	158		
34	4	28	-10	23	11	8	22	-3	41	158		
35	3	12	-56	93	11	15	7	-4	42	158		
36	2	18	86	-63	19	7	15	-5	43	158		
6	57	-668	2799	-9	-10	-11	-1987	43	-62	158		
51	-96	0706	-2761	47	48	49	2025	44	45	158		
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158		

7	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										158
28	29	-18	25	26	27	44	-29	-12	38	158		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	49	-13	39	158		
6	24	07	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	158		
17	13	16	20	25	11	10	20	-14	40	158		
18	12	1	-7	34	44	9	21	-15	41	158		
19	11	48	-10	23	11	8	22	-16	42	158		
-60	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	158		
33	-23	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	158		
-680	-614	3483	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	41	158		
0706	640	-3457	46	47	48	49	2025	41	13	158		
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158		

7	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										158
07	59	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	23	33	158		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	12	8	22	34	158		
1	-7	24	44	-1	21	82	-62	84	-28	158		
38	-10	23	11	-2	22	-8	28	21	35	158		
2	-66	103	1	10	32	-9	29	20	36	158		
18	86	-83	19	32	10	-10	30	19	37	158		
6	112	2637	-4	-686	-2005	10	32	18	38	158		
14	-92	-2617	24	0706	2025	32	10	17	39	158		
-2658	16	2801	15	14	13	12	11	28	-94	158		
2714	40	-2745	41	42	43	44	45	-94	28	158		
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158		

7	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										158
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	21	35	158		
71	07	59	-10	06	-51	-52	72	98	-42	158		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	142	-122	20	36	158		
-3	3	-5	22	42	23	-7	27	19	37	158		
-4	36	-12	25	13	24	-8	28	18	38	158		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	17	39	158		
71	133	-111	-10	-11	-12	10	32	16	40	158		
-51	-113	131	30	31	32	32	10	15	41	158		
-650	-724	3521	13	12	11	10	-1969	28	-94	158		
0706	780	-3465	43	44	45	46	2025	-94	28	158		
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158		

7	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										158
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	-6	42	158		
12	07	61	-14	06	0	20	30	-7	43	158		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	207	-171	158		
10	5	-7	22	40	-1	21	32	-8	44	158		
9	36	-14	27	11	-2	22	33	-9	45	158		
8	2	35	2	1	10	30	34	-10	46	158		
13	18	-15	18	19	30	10	29	-11	47	158		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	-12	48	158		
-664	-670	3478	-1	-2	-3	-1989	-5	18	-4	158		
700	0706	-3442	37	38	39	2025	41	-4	18	158		
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158		

7	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										158
17	-13	20	129	19	18	16	-74	-13	39	158		
25	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	158		
24	11	07	51	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	158		
23	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	158		
22	9	5	-7	12	40	21	30	-16	42	158		
21	12	26	-14	27	11	18	31	-17	43	158		
26	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	158		
-26	65	32	-77	33	34	36	35	-19	45	158		
-20	-79	2954	-680	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	41	158		
46	105	-2928	0706	2025	49	50	51	41	13	158		
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158		

■ 159th Day of the Year - 08.06.2025

8	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										159
-48	41	025	26	27	028	-18	29	19	30	159		
37	38	14	13	12	11	57	10	-64	31	159		
-53	92	08	47	-10	06	10	20	0	39	159		
32	7	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	-1	40	159		
33	6	1	-6	12	44	9	21	127	-88	159		
34	5	26	-10	24	11	8	22	-2	41	159		
35	4	12	-58	95	11	15	6	-3	42	159		
36	3	18	88	-65	19	6	15	-4	43	159		
2	61	-767	2897	-8	-9	-10	-1986	43	-64	159		
51	-98	0806	-2858	47	48	49	2025	44	45	159		
159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159		

8	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										159
28	29	0-18	25	26	27	45	-29	-12	38	159		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	50	-13	39	159		
6	24	08	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	159		
17	13	16	20	25	12	10	20	-14	40	159		
18	12	1	-6	34	44	9	21	-15	41	159		
19	11	48	-10	24	11	8	22	-16	42	159		
-59	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	159		
33	-22	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	159		
-780	-714	3683	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	42	159		
0806	740	-3657	46	47	48	49	2025	42	13	159		
159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159		

8	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										159
08	59	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	23	33	159		
16	20	25	2	43	-23	12	8	22	34	159		
1	-6	24	44	-1	21	82	-62	84	-28	159		
38	-10	24	11	-2	22	-8	28	21	35	159		
2	-66	103	1	10	33	-9	29	20	36	159		
18	86	-83	19	33	10	-10	30	19	37	159		
6	113	2736	-4	-786	-2005	10	33	18	38	159		
14	-93	-2716	24	0806	2025	33	10	17	39	159		
-2756	16	2899	15	14	13	12	11	28	-93	159		
2812	40	-2843	41	42	43	44	45	-93	28	159		
159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159		

8	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										159
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	21	35	159		
72	08	59	-10	06	-52	-50	70	98	-42	159		
-2	16	20	25	2	22	140	-120	20	36	159		
-3	3	-4	22	42	23	-7	27	19	37	159		
-4	36	-12	26	13	24	-8	28	18	38	159		
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	17	39	159		
69	132	-108	-10	-11	-12	10	33	16	40	159		
-49	-112	128	30	31	32	33	10	15	41	159		
-750	-822	3719	13	12	11	10	-1969	28	-93	159		
0806	878	-3663	43	44	45	46	2025	-93	28	159		
159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159		

8	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										159
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	-6	42	159		
13	08	60	-14	06	0	20	30	-7	43	159		
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	207	-171	159		
11	5	-6	21	40	-1	21	32	-8	44	159		
10	35	-14	28	11	-2	22	33	-9	45	159		
9	2	34	3	1	10	30	34	-10	46	159		
14	18	-14	17	19	30	10	29	-11	47	159		
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	-12	48	159		
-766	-770	3680	-1	-2	-3	-1989	-5	18	-3	159		
802	0806	-3644	37	38	39	2025	41	-3	18	159		
159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159		

8	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										159
18	-11	21	122	20	19	17	-73	-13	39	159		
26	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	159		
25	11	08	50	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	159		
24	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	159		
23	9	5	-6	11	40	21	30	-16	42	159		
22	12	25	-14	28	11	18	31	-17	43	159		
27	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	159		
-32	64	32	-69	33	34	36	35	-19	45	159		
-20	-79	3054	-780	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	42	159		
46	105	-3028	0806	2025	49	50	51	42	13	159		
159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159		

■ 160th Day of the Year - 09.06.2025

9	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										160
-48	42	025	26	27	28	-18	29	19	30	160		
37	38	14	13	12	11	57	10	-63	31	160		
-53	92	09	47	-10	06	10	20	0	39	160		
32	7	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	-1	40	160		
33	6	1	-5	12	44	9	21	127	-88	160		
34	5	26	-10	25	11	8	22	-2	41	160		
35	4	12	-58	95	11	15	7	-3	42	160		
36	3	18	88	-65	19	7	15	-4	43	160		
3	60	-867	2997	-8	-9	-10	-1986	43	-63	160		
51	-97	0906	-2958	47	48	49	2025	44	45	160		
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160		

9	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										160
28	29	-018	25	26	27	46	-29	-12	38	160		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	51	-13	39	160		
6	24	09	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	160		
17	13	16	20	25	13	10	20	-14	40	160		
18	12	1	-5	34	44	9	21	-15	41	160		
19	11	48	-10	25	11	8	22	-16	42	160		
-58	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	160		
33	-21	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	160		
-880	-814	3883	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	43	160		
0906	840	-3857	46	47	48	49	2025	43	13	160		
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160		

9	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									160
09	57	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	25	33	160	
16	20	25	1	43	-23	14	6	24	34	160	
1	-5	22	44	-1	21	80	-60	78	-20	160	
36	-10	25	11	-2	22	-8	28	23	35	160	
2	-68	105	1	10	32	-9	29	22	36	160	
18	88	-85	19	32	10	-10	30	21	37	160	
6	112	2837	-4	-886	-2005	10	32	20	38	160	
14	-92	-2817	24	0906	2025	32	10	19	39	160	
-2852	18	2991	17	16	15	14	13	29	-101	160	
2910	40	-2933	41	42	43	44	45	-101	29	160	
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	

9	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									160
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	23	35	160	
71	09	57	-10	06	-51	-54	74	92	-34	160	
-2	16	20	25	1	22	144	-124	22	36	160	
-3	3	-3	20	42	23	-7	27	21	37	160	
-4	34	-12	27	13	24	-8	28	20	38	160	
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	19	39	160	
75	137	-119	-10	-11	-12	10	32	18	40	160	
-55	-117	139	30	31	32	32	10	17	41	160	
-848	-922	3915	15	14	13	12	-1967	29	-101	160	
0906	980	-3857	43	44	45	46	2025	-101	29	160	
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	

9	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									160
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	-4	42	160	
12	09	59	-14	06	0	20	30	-5	43	160	
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	201	-163	160	
10	5	-5	20	40	-1	21	32	-6	44	160	
9	34	-14	29	11	-2	22	33	-7	45	160	
8	2	33	4	1	10	30	34	-8	46	160	
13	18	-13	16	19	30	10	29	-9	47	160	
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	-10	48	160	
-862	-868	3872	1	0	-1	-1987	-3	19	-11	160	
900	0906	-3834	37	38	39	2025	41	-11	19	160	
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	

9	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									160
19	-9	22	115	21	20	18	-72	-13	39	160	
27	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	160	
26	11	09	49	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	160	
25	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	160	
24	9	5	-5	10	40	21	30	-16	42	160	
23	12	24	-14	29	11	18	31	-17	43	160	
28	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	160	
-38	63	32	-61	33	34	36	35	-19	45	160	
-20	-79	3154	-880	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	43	160	
46	105	-3128	0906	2025	49	50	51	43	13	160	
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	

■ 161st Day of the Year - 10.06.2025

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									161
-46	38	25	26	27	28	-15	29	19	30	161	
37	38	15	14	13	12	55	11	-65	31	161	
-50	90	10	45	-10	06	10	20	1	39	161	
32	8	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	0	40	161	
33	7	1	-4	10	44	9	21	125	-85	161	
34	6	24	-10	26	11	8	22	-1	41	161	
35	5	12	-60	97	11	15	6	-2	42	161	
36	4	18	90	-67	19	6	15	-3	43	161	
-1	64	-966	3095	-7	-8	-9	-1985	43	-65	161	
51	-99	1006	-3055	47	48	49	2025	44	45	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

10	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									161
28	29	-18	25	26	27	47	-29	-12	38	161	
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	52	-13	39	161	
6	24	10	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	161	
17	13	16	20	25	14	10	20	-14	40	161	
18	12	1	-4	34	44	9	21	-15	41	161	
19	11	48	-10	26	11	8	22	-16	42	161	
-57	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	161	
33	-20	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	161	
-980	-914	4083	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	44	161	
1006	940	-4057	46	47	48	49	2025	44	13	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									161
10	57	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	25	33	161	
16	20	25	2	43	-23	14	6	24	34	161	
1	-4	22	44	-1	21	80	-60	78	-20	161	
36	-10	26	11	-2	22	-8	28	23	35	161	
2	-68	105	1	10	33	-9	29	22	36	161	
18	88	-85	19	33	10	-10	30	21	37	161	
6	113	2936	-4	-986	-2005	10	33	20	38	161	
14	-93	-2916	24	1006	2025	33	10	19	39	161	
-2950	18	3089	17	16	15	14	13	29	-100	161	
3008	40	-3031	41	42	43	44	45	-100	29	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

10	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									161
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	23	35	161	
72	10	57	-10	06	-52	-52	72	92	-34	161	
-2	16	20	25	2	22	142	-122	22	36	161	
-3	3	-2	20	42	23	-7	27	21	37	161	
-4	34	-12	28	13	24	-8	28	20	38	161	
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	19	39	161	
73	136	-116	-10	-11	-12	10	33	18	40	161	
-53	-116	136	30	31	32	33	10	17	41	161	
-948	-1020	4113	15	14	13	12	-1967	29	-100	161	
1006	1078	-4055	43	44	45	46	2025	-100	29	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									161
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	-4	42	161	
13	10	58	-14	06	0	20	30	-5	43	161	
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	201	-163	161	
11	5	-4	19	40	-1	21	32	-6	44	161	
10	33	-14	30	11	-2	22	33	-7	45	161	
9	2	32	5	1	10	30	34	-8	46	161	
14	18	-12	15	19	30	10	29	-9	47	161	
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	-10	48	161	
-964	-968	4074	1	0	-1	-1987	-3	19	-10	161	
1002	1006	-4036	37	38	39	2025	41	-10	19	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

10	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									161
20	-7	23	108	22	21	19	-71	-13	39	161	
28	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	161	
27	11	10	48	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	161	
26	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	161	
25	9	5	-4	9	40	21	30	-16	42	161	
24	12	23	-14	30	11	18	31	-17	43	161	
29	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	161	
-44	62	32	-53	33	34	36	35	-19	45	161	
-20	-79	3254	-980	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	44	161	
46	105	-3228	1006	2025	49	50	51	44	13	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

■ 162nd Day of the Year - 11.06.2025

11	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									162
-46	39	25	26	27	28	-15	29	19	30	162	
37	38	15	14	13	12	55	11	-64	31	162	
-50	90	11	45	-10	06	10	20	1	39	162	
32	8	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	0	40	162	
33	7	1	-3	10	44	9	21	125	-85	162	
34	6	24	-10	27	11	8	22	-1	41	162	
35	5	12	-60	97	11	15	7	-2	42	162	
36	4	18	90	-67	19	7	15	-3	43	162	
0	63	-1066	3195	-7	-8	-9	-1985	43	-64	162	
51	-98	1106	-3155	47	48	49	2025	44	45	162	
162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	

11	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									162
28	29	-18	25	26	27	48	-29	-12	38	162	
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	53	-13	39	162	
6	24	11	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	162	
17	13	16	20	25	15	10	20	-14	40	162	
18	12	1	-3	34	44	9	21	-15	41	162	
19	11	48	-10	27	11	8	22	-16	42	162	
-56	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	162	
33	-19	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	162	
-1080	-1014	4283	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	45	162	
1106	1040	-4257	46	47	48	49	2025	45	13	162	
162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	

11	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										162
11	55	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	27	33	162		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	16	4	26	34	162		
1	-3	20	44	-1	21	78	-58	72	-12	162		
34	-10	27	11	-2	22	-8	28	25	35	162		
2	-70	107	1	10	32	-9	29	24	36	162		
18	90	-87	19	32	10	-10	30	23	37	162		
6	112	3037	-4	-1086	-2005	10	32	22	38	162		
14	-92	-3017	24	1106	2025	32	10	21	39	162		
-3046	20	3181	19	18	17	16	15	30	-108	162		
3106	40	-3121	41	42	43	44	45	-108	30	162		
162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162		

11	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										162
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	25	35	162		
71	11	55	-10	06	-51	-56	76	86	-26	162		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	146	-126	24	36	162		
-3	3	-1	18	42	23	-7	27	23	37	162		
-4	32	-12	29	13	24	-8	28	22	38	162		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	21	39	162		
79	141	-127	-10	-11	-12	10	32	20	40	162		
-59	-121	147	30	31	32	32	10	19	41	162		
-1046	-1120	4309	17	16	15	14	-1965	30	-108	162		
1106	1180	-4249	43	44	45	46	2025	-108	30	162		
162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162		

11	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										162
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	-2	42	162		
12	11	57	-14	06	0	20	30	-3	43	162		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	195	-155	162		
10	5	-3	18	40	-1	21	32	-4	44	162		
9	32	-14	31	11	-2	22	33	-5	45	162		
8	2	31	6	1	10	30	34	-6	46	162		
13	18	-11	14	19	30	10	29	-7	47	162		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	-8	48	162		
-1060	-1066	4266	3	2	1	-1985	-1	20	-18	162		
1100	1106	-4226	37	38	39	2025	41	-18	20	162		
162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162		

11	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										162
21	-5	24	101	23	22	20	-70	-13	39	162		
29	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	162		
28	11	11	47	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	162		
27	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	162		
26	9	5	-3	8	40	21	30	-16	42	162		
25	12	22	-14	31	11	18	31	-17	43	162		
30	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	162		
-50	61	32	-45	33	34	36	35	-19	45	162		
-20	-79	3354	-1080	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	45	162		
46	105	-3328	1106	2025	49	50	51	45	13	162		
162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162		

■ 163rd Day of the Year - 12.06.2025

12	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
-44	35	25	26	27	28	-12	29	19	30	163		
37	38	16	15	14	13	53	12	-66	31	163		
-47	88	12	43	-10	06	10	20	2	39	163		
32	9	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	1	40	163		
33	8	1	-2	8	44	9	21	123	-82	163		
34	7	22	-10	28	11	8	22	0	41	163		
35	6	12	-62	99	11	15	6	-1	42	163		
36	5	18	92	-69	019	6	15	-2	43	163		
-4	67	-1165	3293	-6	-7	-8	-1984	43	-66	163		
51	-100	1206	-3252	47	48	49	2025	44	45	163		
163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163		

12	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										163
28	29	-18	25	26	27	49	-29	-12	38	163		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	54	-13	39	163		
6	24	12	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	163		
17	13	16	20	25	16	10	20	-14	40	163		
18	12	1	-2	34	44	9	21	-15	41	163		
19	11	48	-10	28	11	8	22	-16	42	163		
-55	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	163		
33	-18	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	163		
-1180	-1114	4483	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	46	163		
1206	1140	-4457	46	47	48	49	2025	46	13	163		
163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163		

12	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
12	55	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	27	33	163		
16	20	25	2	43	-23	16	4	26	34	163		
1	-2	20	44	-1	21	78	-58	72	-12	163		
34	-10	28	11	-2	22	-8	28	25	35	163		
2	-70	107	1	10	33	-9	29	24	36	163		
18	90	-87	19	33	10	-10	30	23	37	163		
6	113	3136	-4	-1186	-2005	10	33	22	38	163		
14	-93	-3116	24	1206	2025	33	10	21	39	163		
-3144	20	3279	19	18	17	16	15	30	-107	163		
3204	40	-3219	41	42	43	44	45	-107	30	163		
163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163		

12	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										163
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	25	35	163		
72	12	55	-10	06	-52	-54	74	86	-26	163		
-2	16	20	25	2	22	144	-124	24	36	163		
-3	3	0	18	42	23	-7	27	23	37	163		
-4	32	-12	30	13	24	-8	28	22	38	163		
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	21	39	163		
77	140	-124	-10	-11	-12	10	33	20	40	163		
-57	-120	144	30	31	32	33	10	19	41	163		
-1146	-1218	4507	17	16	15	14	-1965	30	-107	163		
1206	1278	-4447	43	44	45	46	2025	-107	30	163		
163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163		

12	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	-2	42	163		
13	12	56	-14	06	0	20	30	-3	43	163		
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	195	-155	163		
11	5	-2	17	40	-1	21	32	-4	44	163		
10	31	-14	32	11	-2	22	33	-5	45	163		
9	2	30	7	1	10	30	34	-6	46	163		
14	18	-10	13	19	30	10	29	-7	47	163		
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	-8	48	163		
-1162	-1166	4468	3	2	1	-1985	-1	20	-17	163		
1202	1206	-4428	37	38	39	2025	41	-17	20	163		
163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163		

12	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										163
22	-3	25	94	24	23	21	-69	-13	39	163		
30	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	163		
29	11	12	46	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	163		
28	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	163		
27	9	5	-2	7	40	21	30	-16	42	163		
26	12	21	-14	32	11	18	31	-17	43	163		
31	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	163		
-56	60	32	-37	33	34	36	35	-19	45	163		
-20	-79	3454	-1180	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	46	163		
46	105	-3428	1206	2025	49	50	51	46	13	163		
163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163		

■ 164th Day of the Year - 13.06.2025

13	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164
-44	36	25	26	27	28	-12	29	19	30	164		
37	38	16	15	14	13	53	12	-65	31	164		
-47	88	13	43	-10	06	10	20	2	39	164		
32	9	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	1	40	164		
33	8	1	-1	8	44	9	21	123	-82	164		
34	7	22	-10	29	11	8	22	0	41	164		
35	6	12	-62	99	11	15	7	-1	42	164		
36	5	18	92	-69	19	7	15	-2	43	164		
-3	66	-1265	3393	-6	-7	-8	-1984	43	-65	164		
51	-99	1306	-3352	47	48	49	2025	44	45	164		
164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164		

13	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										164
28	29	-18	25	26	27	50	-29	-12	38	164		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	55	-13	39	164		
6	24	13	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	164		
17	13	16	20	25	17	10	20	-14	40	164		
18	12	1	-1	34	44	9	21	-15	41	164		
19	11	48	-10	29	11	8	22	-16	42	164		
-54	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	164		
33	-17	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	164		
-1280	-1214	4683	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	47	164		
1306	1240	-4657	46	47	48	49	2025	47	13	164		
164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164		

13	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164
13	53	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	29	33	164		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	18	2	28	34	164		
1	-1	18	44	-1	21	76	-56	66	-4	164		
32	-10	29	11	-2	22	-8	28	27	35	164		
2	-72	109	1	10	32	-9	29	26	36	164		
18	92	-89	19	32	10	-10	30	25	37	164		
6	112	3237	-4	-1286	-2005	10	32	24	38	164		
14	-92	-3217	24	1306	2025	32	10	23	39	164		
-3240	22	3371	21	20	19	18	17	31	-115	164		
3302	40	-3309	41	42	43	44	45	-115	31	164		
164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164		

13	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										164
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	27	35	164		
71	13	53	-10	06	-51	-58	78	80	-18	164		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	148	-128	26	36	164		
-3	3	1	16	42	23	-7	27	25	37	164		
-4	30	-12	31	13	24	-8	28	24	38	164		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	23	39	164		
83	145	-135	-10	-11	-12	10	32	22	40	164		
-63	-125	155	30	31	32	32	10	21	41	164		
-1244	-1318	4703	19	18	17	16	-1963	31	-115	164		
1306	1380	-4641	43	44	45	46	2025	-115	31	164		
164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164		

13	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	0	42	164		
12	13	55	-14	06	0	20	30	-1	43	164		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	189	-147	164		
10	5	-1	16	40	-1	21	32	-2	44	164		
9	30	-14	33	11	-2	22	33	-3	45	164		
8	2	29	8	1	10	30	34	-4	46	164		
13	18	-9	12	19	30	10	29	-5	47	164		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	-6	48	164		
-1258	-1264	4660	5	4	3	-1983	1	21	-25	164		
1300	1306	-4618	37	38	39	2025	41	-25	21	164		
164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164		

13	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										164
23	-1	26	87	25	24	22	-68	-13	39	164		
31	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	164		
30	11	13	45	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	164		
29	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	164		
28	9	5	-1	6	40	21	30	-16	42	164		
27	12	20	-14	33	11	18	31	-17	43	164		
32	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	164		
-62	59	32	-29	33	34	36	35	-19	45	164		
-20	-79	3554	-1280	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	47	164		
46	105	-3528	1306	2025	49	50	51	47	13	164		
164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164		

■ 165th Day of the Year - 14.06.2025

14	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									165
-42	32	25	26	27	028	-9	29	19	30	165	
37	38	17	16	15	14	51	13	-67	31	165	
-44	86	14	41	-10	06	10	20	3	39	165	
32	10	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	2	40	165	
33	9	1	0	6	44	9	21	121	-79	165	
34	8	20	-10	30	11	8	22	1	41	165	
35	7	12	-64	101	11	15	6	0	42	165	
36	6	18	94	-71	19	6	15	-1	43	165	
-7	70	-1364	3491	-5	-6	-7	-1983	43	-67	165	
51	-101	1406	-3449	47	48	49	2025	44	45	165	
165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	

14	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									165
28	29	-18	25	26	27	51	-29	-12	38	165	
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	56	-13	39	165	
6	24	14	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	165	
17	13	16	20	25	18	10	20	-14	40	165	
18	12	1	0	34	44	9	21	-15	41	165	
19	11	48	-10	30	11	8	22	-16	42	165	
-53	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	165	
33	-16	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	165	
-1380	-1314	4883	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	48	165	
1406	1340	-4857	46	47	48	49	2025	48	13	165	
165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	

14	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									165
14	53	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	29	33	165	
16	20	25	2	43	-23	18	2	28	34	165	
1	0	18	44	-1	21	76	-56	66	-4	165	
32	-10	30	11	-2	22	-8	28	27	35	165	
2	-72	109	1	10	33	-9	29	26	36	165	
18	92	-89	19	33	10	-10	30	25	37	165	
6	113	3336	-4	-1386	-2005	10	33	24	38	165	
14	-93	-3316	24	1406	2025	33	10	23	39	165	
-3338	22	3469	21	20	19	18	17	31	-114	165	
3400	40	-3407	41	42	43	44	45	-114	31	165	
165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	

14	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									165
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	27	35	165	
72	14	53	-10	06	-52	-56	76	80	-18	165	
-2	16	20	25	2	22	146	-126	26	36	165	
-3	3	2	16	42	23	-7	27	25	37	165	
-4	30	-12	32	13	24	-8	28	24	38	165	
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	23	39	165	
81	144	-132	-10	-11	-12	10	33	22	40	165	
-61	-124	152	30	31	32	33	10	21	41	165	
-1344	-1416	4901	19	18	17	16	-1963	31	-114	165	
1406	1478	-4839	43	44	45	46	2025	-114	31	165	
165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	

14	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										165
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	0	42	165		
13	14	54	-14	06	0	20	30	-1	43	165		
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	189	-147	165		
11	5	0	15	40	-1	21	32	-2	44	165		
10	29	-14	34	11	-2	22	33	-3	45	165		
9	2	28	9	1	10	30	34	-4	46	165		
14	18	-8	11	19	30	10	29	-5	47	165		
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	-6	48	165		
-1360	-1364	4862	5	4	3	-1983	1	21	-24	165		
1402	1406	-4820	37	38	39	2025	41	-24	21	165		
165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165		

14	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										165
24	1	27	80	26	25	23	-67	-13	39	165		
32	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	165		
31	11	14	44	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	165		
30	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	165		
29	9	5	0	5	40	21	30	-16	42	165		
28	12	19	-14	34	11	18	31	-17	43	165		
33	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	165		
-68	58	32	-21	33	34	36	35	-19	45	165		
-20	-79	3654	-1380	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	48	165		
46	105	-3628	1406	2025	49	50	51	48	13	165		
165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165		

■ 166th Day of the Year - 15.06.2025

15	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166
-42	33	25	26	27	28	-9	29	19	30	166		
37	38	17	16	15	14	51	13	-66	31	166		
-44	86	15	41	-10	06	10	20	3	39	166		
32	10	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	2	40	166		
33	9	1	1	6	44	9	21	121	-79	166		
34	8	20	-10	31	11	8	22	1	41	166		
35	7	12	-64	101	11	15	7	0	42	166		
36	6	18	94	-71	19	7	15	-1	43	166		
-6	69	-1464	3591	-5	-6	-7	-1983	43	-66	166		
51	-100	1506	-3549	47	48	49	2025	44	45	166		
166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166		

15	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										166
28	29	-18	25	26	27	52	-29	-12	38	166		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	57	-13	39	166		
6	24	15	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	166		
17	13	16	20	25	19	10	20	-14	40	166		
18	12	1	1	34	44	9	21	-15	41	166		
19	11	48	-10	31	11	8	22	-16	42	166		
-52	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	166		
33	-15	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	166		
-1480	-1414	5083	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	49	166		
1506	1440	-5057	46	47	48	49	2025	49	13	166		
166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166		

15	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166
15	51	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	31	33	166		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	20	0	30	34	166		
1	1	16	44	-1	21	74	-54	60	4	166		
30	-10	31	11	-2	22	-8	28	29	35	166		
2	-74	111	1	10	32	-9	29	28	36	166		
18	94	-91	19	32	10	-10	30	27	37	166		
6	112	3437	-4	-1486	-2005	10	32	26	38	166		
14	-92	-3417	24	1506	2025	32	10	25	39	166		
-3434	24	3561	23	22	21	20	19	32	-122	166		
3498	40	-3497	41	42	43	44	45	-122	32	166		
166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166		

15	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										166
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	29	35	166		
71	15	51	-10	06	-51	-60	80	74	-10	166		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	150	-130	28	36	166		
-3	3	3	14	42	23	-7	27	27	37	166		
-4	28	-12	33	13	24	-8	28	26	38	166		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	25	39	166		
87	149	-143	-10	-11	-12	10	32	24	40	166		
-67	-129	163	30	31	32	32	10	23	41	166		
-1442	-1516	5097	21	20	19	18	-1961	32	-122	166		
1506	1580	-5033	43	44	45	46	2025	-122	32	166		
166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166		

15	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	2	42	166		
12	15	53	-14	06	0	20	30	1	43	166		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	183	-139	166		
10	5	1	14	40	-1	21	32	0	44	166		
9	28	-14	35	11	-2	22	33	-1	45	166		
8	2	27	10	1	10	30	34	-2	46	166		
13	18	-7	10	19	30	10	29	-3	47	166		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	-4	48	166		
-1456	-1462	5054	7	6	5	-1981	3	22	-32	166		
1500	1506	-5010	37	38	39	2025	41	-32	22	166		
166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166		

15	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										166
25	3	28	73	27	26	24	-66	-13	39	166		
33	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	166		
32	11	15	43	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	166		
31	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	166		
30	9	5	1	4	40	21	30	-16	42	166		
29	12	18	-14	35	11	18	31	-17	43	166		
34	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	166		
-74	57	32	-13	33	34	36	35	-19	45	166		
-20	-79	3754	-1480	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	49	166		
46	105	-3728	1506	2025	49	50	51	49	13	166		
166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166		

■ 167th Day of the Year - 16.06.2025

16	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										167
-40	29	25	26	27	28	-6	29	19	30	167		
37	38	18	17	16	15	49	14	-68	31	167		
-41	84	16	39	-10	06	10	20	4	39	167		
32	11	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	3	40	167		
33	10	1	2	4	44	9	21	119	-76	167		
34	9	18	-10	32	11	8	22	2	41	167		
35	8	12	-66	103	11	15	6	1	42	167		
36	7	18	96	-73	19	6	15	0	43	167		
-10	73	-1563	3689	-4	0-5	-6	-1982	43	-68	167		
51	-102	1606	-3646	47	48	49	2025	44	45	167		
167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167		

16	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										167
28	29	-18	25	26	27	53	-29	-12	38	167		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	58	-13	39	167		
6	24	16	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	167		
17	13	16	20	25	20	10	20	-14	40	167		
18	12	1	2	34	44	9	21	-15	41	167		
19	11	48	-10	32	11	8	22	-16	42	167		
-51	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	167		
33	-14	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	167		
-1580	-1514	5283	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	50	167		
1606	1540	-5257	46	47	48	49	2025	50	13	167		
167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167		

16	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										167
16	51	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	31	33	167		
16	20	25	2	43	-23	20	0	30	34	167		
1	2	16	44	-1	21	74	-54	60	4	167		
30	-10	32	11	-2	22	-8	28	29	35	167		
2	-74	111	1	10	33	-9	29	28	36	167		
18	94	-91	19	33	10	-10	30	27	37	167		
6	113	3536	-4	-1586	-2005	10	33	26	38	167		
14	-93	-3516	24	1606	2025	33	10	25	39	167		
-3532	24	3659	23	22	21	20	19	32	-121	167		
3596	40	-3595	41	42	43	44	45	-121	32	167		
167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167		

16	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										167
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	29	35	167		
72	16	51	-10	06	-52	-58	78	74	-10	167		
-2	16	20	25	2	22	148	-128	28	36	167		
-3	3	4	14	42	23	-7	27	27	37	167		
-4	28	-12	34	13	24	-8	28	26	38	167		
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	25	39	167		
85	148	-140	-10	-11	-12	10	33	24	40	167		
-65	-128	160	30	31	32	33	10	23	41	167		
-1542	-1614	5295	21	20	19	18	-1961	32	-121	167		
1606	1678	-5231	43	44	45	46	2025	-121	32	167		
167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167		

16	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										167
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	2	42	167		
13	16	52	-14	06	0	20	30	1	43	167		
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	183	-139	167		
11	5	2	13	40	-1	21	32	0	44	167		
10	27	-14	36	11	-2	22	33	-1	45	167		
9	2	26	11	1	10	30	34	-2	46	167		
14	18	-6	9	19	30	10	29	-3	47	167		
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	-4	48	167		
-1558	-1562	5256	7	6	5	-1981	3	22	-31	167		
1602	1606	-5212	37	38	39	2025	41	-31	22	167		
167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167		

16	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										167
26	5	29	66	28	27	25	-65	-13	39	167		
34	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	167		
33	11	16	42	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	167		
32	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	167		
31	9	5	2	3	40	21	30	-16	42	167		
30	12	17	-14	36	11	18	31	-17	43	167		
35	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	167		
-80	56	32	-5	33	34	36	35	-19	45	167		
-20	-79	3854	-1580	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	50	167		
46	105	-3828	1606	2025	49	50	51	50	13	167		
167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167		

■ 168th Day of the Year - 17.06.2025

17	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168
-40	30	25	26	27	28	-6	29	19	30	168		
37	38	18	17	16	15	49	14	-67	31	168		
-41	84	17	39	-10	06	10	20	4	39	168		
32	11	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	3	40	168		
33	10	1	3	4	44	9	21	119	-76	168		
34	9	18	-10	33	11	8	22	2	41	168		
35	8	12	-66	103	11	15	7	1	42	168		
36	7	18	96	-73	19	7	15	0	43	168		
-9	72	-1663	3789	-4	-5	-6	-1982	43	-67	168		
51	-101	1706	-3746	47	48	49	2025	44	45	168		
168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168		

17	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										168
28	29	-18	25	26	27	54	-29	-12	38	168		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	59	-13	39	168		
6	24	17	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	168		
17	13	16	20	25	21	10	20	-14	40	168		
18	12	1	3	34	44	9	21	-15	41	168		
19	11	48	-10	33	11	8	22	-16	42	168		
-50	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	168		
33	-13	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	168		
-1680	-1614	5483	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	51	168		
1706	1640	-5457	46	47	48	49	2025	51	13	168		
168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168		

17	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168
17	49	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	33	33	168		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	22	-2	32	34	168		
1	3	14	44	-1	21	72	-52	54	12	168		
28	-10	33	11	-2	22	-8	28	31	35	168		
2	-76	113	1	10	32	-9	29	30	36	168		
18	96	-93	19	32	10	-10	30	29	37	168		
6	112	3637	-4	-1686	-2005	10	32	28	38	168		
14	-92	-3617	24	1706	2025	32	10	27	39	168		
-3628	26	3751	25	24	23	22	21	33	-129	168		
3694	40	-3685	41	42	43	44	45	-129	33	168		
168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168		

17	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										168
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	31	35	168		
71	17	49	-10	06	-51	-62	82	68	-2	168		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	152	-132	30	36	168		
-3	3	5	12	42	23	-7	27	29	37	168		
-4	26	-12	35	13	24	-8	28	28	38	168		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	27	39	168		
91	153	-151	-10	-11	-12	10	32	26	40	168		
-71	-133	171	30	31	32	32	10	25	41	168		
-1640	-1714	5491	23	22	21	20	-1959	33	-129	168		
1706	1780	-5425	43	44	45	46	2025	-129	33	168		
168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168		

17	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	4	42	168		
12	17	51	-14	06	0	20	30	3	43	168		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	177	-131	168		
10	5	3	12	40	-1	21	32	2	44	168		
9	26	-14	37	11	-2	22	33	1	45	168		
8	2	25	12	1	10	30	34	0	46	168		
13	18	-5	8	19	30	10	29	-1	47	168		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	-2	48	168		
-1654	-1660	5448	9	8	7	-1979	5	23	-39	168		
1700	1706	-5402	37	38	39	2025	41	-39	23	168		
168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168		

17	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										168
27	7	30	59	29	28	26	-64	-13	39	168		
35	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	168		
34	11	17	41	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	168		
33	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	168		
32	9	5	3	2	40	21	30	-16	42	168		
31	12	16	-14	37	11	18	31	-17	43	168		
36	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	168		
-86	55	32	3	33	34	36	35	-19	45	168		
-20	-79	3954	-1680	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	51	168		
46	105	-3928	1706	2025	49	50	51	51	13	168		
168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168		

■ 169th Day of the Year - 18.06.2025

18	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										169
-38	26	25	26	27	28	-3	29	19	30	169		
37	38	19	18	17	16	47	15	-69	31	169		
-38	82	18	37	-10	06	10	20	5	39	169		
32	12	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	4	40	169		
33	11	1	4	2	44	9	21	117	-73	169		
34	10	16	-10	34	11	8	22	3	41	169		
35	9	12	-68	105	11	15	6	2	42	169		
36	8	18	98	-75	19	6	15	1	43	169		
-13	76	-1762	3887	-3	-4	-5	-1981	43	-69	169		
51	-103	1806	-3843	47	48	49	2025	44	45	169		
169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169		

18	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										169
28	29	-18	25	26	27	55	-29	-12	38	169		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	60	-13	39	169		
6	24	18	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	169		
17	13	16	20	25	22	10	20	-14	40	169		
18	12	1	4	34	44	9	21	-15	41	169		
19	11	48	-10	34	11	8	22	-16	42	169		
-49	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	169		
33	-12	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	169		
-1780	-1714	5683	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	52	169		
1806	1740	-5657	46	47	48	49	2025	52	13	169		
169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169		

18	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										169
18	49	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	33	33	169		
16	20	25	2	43	-23	22	-2	32	34	169		
1	4	14	44	-1	21	72	-52	54	12	169		
28	-10	34	11	-2	22	-8	28	31	35	169		
2	-76	113	1	10	33	-9	29	30	36	169		
18	96	-93	19	33	10	-10	30	29	37	169		
6	113	3736	-4	-1786	-2005	10	33	28	38	169		
14	-93	-3716	24	1806	2025	33	10	27	39	169		
-3726	26	3849	25	24	23	22	21	33	-128	169		
3792	40	-3783	41	42	43	44	45	-128	33	169		
169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169		

18	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										169
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	31	35	169		
72	18	49	-10	06	-52	-60	80	68	-2	169		
-2	16	20	25	2	22	150	-130	30	36	169		
-3	3	6	12	42	23	-7	27	29	37	169		
-4	26	-12	36	13	24	-8	28	28	38	169		
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	27	39	169		
89	152	-148	-10	-11	-12	10	33	26	40	169		
-69	-132	168	30	31	32	33	10	25	41	169		
-1740	-1812	5689	23	22	21	20	-1959	33	-128	169		
1806	1878	-5623	43	44	45	46	2025	-128	33	169		
169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169		

18	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										169
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	4	42	169		
13	18	50	-14	06	0	20	30	3	43	169		
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	177	-131	169		
11	5	4	11	40	-1	21	32	2	44	169		
10	25	-14	38	11	-2	22	33	1	45	169		
9	2	24	13	1	10	30	34	0	46	169		
14	18	-4	7	19	30	10	29	-1	47	169		
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	-2	48	169		
-1756	-1760	5650	9	8	7	-1979	5	23	-38	169		
1802	1806	-5604	37	38	39	2025	41	-38	23	169		
169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169		

18	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										169
28	9	31	52	30	29	27	-63	-13	39	169		
36	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	169		
35	11	18	40	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	169		
34	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	169		
33	9	5	4	1	40	21	30	-16	42	169		
32	12	15	-14	38	11	18	31	-17	43	169		
37	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	169		
-92	54	32	11	33	34	36	35	-19	45	169		
-20	-79	4054	-1780	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	52	169		
46	105	-4028	1806	2025	49	50	51	52	13	169		
169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169		

■ 170th Day of the Year - 19.06.2025

19	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170
-38	27	25	26	27	28	-3	29	19	30	170		
37	38	19	18	17	16	47	15	-68	31	170		
-38	82	19	37	-10	06	10	20	5	39	170		
32	12	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	4	40	170		
33	11	1	5	2	44	9	21	117	-73	170		
34	10	16	-10	35	11	8	22	3	41	170		
35	9	12	-68	105	11	15	7	2	42	170		
36	8	18	98	-75	19	7	15	1	43	170		
-12	75	-1862	3987	-3	-4	-5	-1981	43	-68	170		
51	-102	1906	-3943	47	48	49	2025	44	45	170		
170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		

19	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										170
28	29	-18	25	26	27	56	-29	-12	38	170		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	61	-13	39	170		
6	24	19	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	170		
17	13	16	20	25	23	10	20	-14	40	170		
18	12	1	5	34	44	9	21	-15	41	170		
19	11	48	-10	35	11	8	22	-16	42	170		
-48	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	170		
33	-11	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	170		
-1880	-1814	5883	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	53	170		
1906	1840	-5857	46	47	48	49	2025	53	13	170		
170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		

19	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170
19	47	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	35	33	170		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	24	-4	34	34	170		
1	5	12	44	-1	21	70	-50	48	20	170		
26	-10	35	11	-2	22	-8	28	33	35	170		
2	-78	115	1	10	32	-9	29	32	36	170		
18	98	-95	19	32	10	-10	30	31	37	170		
6	112	3837	-4	-1886	-2005	10	32	30	38	170		
14	-92	-3817	24	1906	2025	32	10	29	39	170		
-3822	28	3941	27	26	25	24	23	34	-136	170		
3890	40	-3873	41	42	43	44	45	-136	34	170		
170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		

19	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										170
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	33	35	170		
71	19	47	-10	06	-51	-64	84	62	6	170		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	154	-134	32	36	170		
-3	3	7	10	42	23	-7	27	31	37	170		
-4	24	-12	37	13	24	-8	28	30	38	170		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	29	39	170		
95	157	-159	-10	-11	-12	10	32	28	40	170		
-75	-137	179	30	31	32	32	10	27	41	170		
-1838	-1912	5885	25	24	23	22	-1957	34	-136	170		
1906	1980	-5817	43	44	45	46	2025	-136	34	170		
170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		

19	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	6	42	170		
12	19	49	-14	06	0	20	30	5	43	170		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	171	-123	170		
10	5	5	10	40	-1	21	32	4	44	170		
9	24	-14	39	11	-2	22	33	3	45	170		
8	2	23	14	1	10	30	34	2	46	170		
13	18	-3	6	19	30	10	29	1	47	170		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	0	48	170		
-1852	-1858	5842	11	10	9	-1977	7	24	-46	170		
1900	1906	-5794	37	38	39	2025	41	-46	24	170		
170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		

19	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										170
29	11	32	45	31	30	28	-62	-13	39	170		
37	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	170		
36	11	19	39	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	170		
35	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	170		
34	9	5	5	0	40	21	30	-16	42	170		
33	12	14	-14	39	11	18	31	-17	43	170		
38	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	170		
-98	53	32	19	33	34	36	35	-19	45	170		
-20	-79	4154	-1880	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	53	170		
46	105	-4128	1906	2025	49	50	51	53	13	170		
170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		

■ 171st Day of the Year - 20.06.2025

20	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									171
-36	23	25	26	27	28	0	29	19	30	171	
37	38	20	19	18	17	45	16	-70	31	171	
-35	80	20	35	-10	06	10	20	6	39	171	
32	13	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	5	40	171	
33	12	1	6	0	44	9	21	115	-70	171	
34	11	14	-10	36	11	8	22	4	41	171	
35	10	12	-70	107	11	15	6	3	42	171	
36	9	18	100	-77	19	6	15	2	43	171	
-16	79	-1961	4085	-2	-3	-4	-1980	43	-70	171	
51	-104	2006	-4040	47	48	49	2025	44	45	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	

20	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									171
28	29	-18	25	26	27	57	-29	-12	38	171	
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	62	-13	39	171	
6	24	20	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	171	
17	13	16	20	25	24	10	20	-14	40	171	
18	12	1	6	34	44	9	21	-15	41	171	
19	11	48	-10	36	11	8	22	-16	42	171	
-47	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	171	
33	-10	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	171	
-1980	-1914	6083	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	54	171	
2006	1940	-6057	46	47	48	49	2025	54	13	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	

20	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									171
20	47	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	35	33	171	
16	20	25	2	43	-23	24	-4	34	34	171	
1	6	12	44	-1	21	70	-50	48	20	171	
26	-10	36	11	-2	22	-8	28	33	35	171	
2	-78	115	1	10	33	-9	29	32	36	171	
18	98	-95	19	33	10	-10	30	31	37	171	
6	113	3936	-4	-1986	-2005	10	33	30	38	171	
14	-93	-3916	24	2006	2025	33	10	29	39	171	
-3920	28	4039	27	26	25	24	23	34	-135	171	
3988	40	-3971	41	42	43	44	45	-135	34	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	

20	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									171
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	33	35	171	
72	20	47	-10	06	-52	-62	82	62	6	171	
-2	16	20	25	2	22	152	-132	32	36	171	
-3	3	8	10	42	23	-7	27	31	37	171	
-4	24	-12	38	13	24	-8	28	30	38	171	
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	29	39	171	
93	156	-156	-10	-11	-12	10	33	28	40	171	
-73	-136	176	30	31	32	33	10	27	41	171	
-1938	-2010	6083	25	24	23	22	-1957	34	-135	171	
2006	2078	-6015	43	44	45	46	2025	-135	34	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	

20	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										171
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	6	42	171		
13	20	48	-14	06	0	20	30	5	43	171		
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	171	-123	171		
11	5	6	9	40	-1	21	32	4	44	171		
10	23	-14	40	11	-2	22	33	3	45	171		
9	2	22	15	1	10	30	34	2	46	171		
14	18	-2	5	19	30	10	29	1	47	171		
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	0	48	171		
-1954	-1958	6044	11	10	9	-1977	7	24	-45	171		
2002	2006	-5996	37	38	39	2025	41	-45	24	171		
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171		

20	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										171
30	13	33	38	32	31	29	-61	-13	39	171		
38	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	171		
37	11	20	38	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	171		
36	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	171		
35	9	5	6	-1	40	21	30	-16	42	171		
34	12	13	-14	40	11	18	31	-17	43	171		
39	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	171		
-104	52	32	27	33	34	36	35	-19	45	171		
-20	-79	4254	-1980	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	54	171		
46	105	-4228	2006	2025	49	50	51	54	13	171		
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171		

■ 172nd Day of the Year - 21.06.2025

21	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172
-36	24	25	26	27	28	0	29	19	30	172		
37	38	20	19	18	17	45	16	-69	31	172		
-35	80	21	35	-10	06	10	20	6	39	172		
32	13	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	5	40	172		
33	12	1	7	0	44	9	21	115	-70	172		
34	11	14	-10	37	11	8	22	4	41	172		
35	10	12	-70	107	11	15	7	3	42	172		
36	9	18	100	-77	19	7	15	2	43	172		
-15	78	-2061	4185	-2	-3	-4	-1980	43	-69	172		
51	-103	2106	-4140	47	48	49	2025	44	45	172		
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172		

21	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										172
28	29	-18	25	26	27	58	-29	-12	38	172		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	63	-13	39	172		
6	24	21	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	172		
17	13	16	20	25	25	10	20	-14	40	172		
18	12	1	7	34	44	9	21	-15	41	172		
19	11	48	-10	37	11	8	22	-16	42	172		
-46	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	172		
33	-9	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	172		
-2080	-2014	6283	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	55	172		
2106	2040	-6257	46	47	48	49	2025	55	13	172		
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172		

21	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172
21	45	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	37	33	172		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	26	-6	36	34	172		
1	7	10	44	-1	21	68	-48	42	28	172		
24	-10	37	11	-2	22	-8	28	35	35	172		
2	-80	117	1	10	32	-9	29	34	36	172		
18	100	-97	19	32	10	-10	30	33	37	172		
6	112	4037	-4	-2086	-2005	10	32	32	38	172		
14	-92	-4017	24	2106	2025	32	10	31	39	172		
-4016	30	4131	29	28	27	26	25	35	-143	172		
4086	40	-4061	41	42	43	44	45	-143	35	172		
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172		

21	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										172
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	35	35	172		
71	21	45	-10	06	-51	-66	86	56	14	172		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	156	-136	34	36	172		
-3	3	9	8	42	23	-7	27	33	37	172		
-4	22	-12	39	13	24	-8	28	32	38	172		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	31	39	172		
99	161	-167	-10	-11	-12	10	32	30	40	172		
-79	-141	187	30	31	32	32	10	29	41	172		
-2036	-2110	6279	27	26	25	24	-1955	35	-143	172		
2106	2180	-6209	43	44	45	46	2025	-143	35	172		
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172		

21	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	8	42	172		
12	21	47	-14	06	0	20	30	7	43	172		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	165	-115	172		
10	5	7	8	40	-1	21	32	6	44	172		
9	22	-14	41	11	-2	22	33	5	45	172		
8	2	21	16	1	10	30	34	4	46	172		
13	18	-1	4	19	30	10	29	3	47	172		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	2	48	172		
-2050	-2056	6236	13	12	11	-1975	9	25	-53	172		
2100	2106	-6186	37	38	39	2025	41	-53	25	172		
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172		

21	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										172
31	15	34	31	33	32	30	-60	-13	39	172		
39	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	172		
38	11	21	37	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	172		
37	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	172		
36	9	5	7	-2	40	21	30	-16	42	172		
35	12	12	-14	41	11	18	31	-17	43	172		
40	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	172		
-110	51	32	35	33	34	36	35	-19	45	172		
-20	-79	4354	-2080	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	55	172		
46	105	-4328	2106	2025	49	50	51	55	13	172		
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172		

■ 173rd Day of the Year - 22.06.2025

22	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
-34	20	25	26	27	28	3	29	19	30	173		
37	38	21	20	19	18	43	17	-71	31	173		
-32	78	22	33	-10	06	10	20	7	39	173		
32	14	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	6	40	173		
33	13	1	8	-2	44	9	21	113	-67	173		
34	12	12	-10	38	11	8	22	5	41	173		
35	11	12	-72	109	11	15	6	4	42	173		
36	10	18	102	-79	19	6	15	3	43	173		
-19	82	-2160	4283	-1	-2	-3	-1979	43	-71	173		
51	-105	2206	-4237	47	48	49	2025	44	45	173		
173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173		

22	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										173
28	29	-18	25	26	27	59	-29	-12	38	173		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	64	-13	39	173		
6	24	22	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	173		
17	13	16	20	25	26	10	20	-14	40	173		
18	12	1	8	34	44	9	21	-15	41	173		
19	11	48	-10	38	11	8	22	-16	42	173		
-45	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	173		
33	-8	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	173		
-2180	-2114	6483	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	56	173		
2206	2140	-6457	46	47	48	49	2025	56	13	173		
173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173		

22	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
22	45	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	37	33	173		
16	20	25	2	43	-23	26	-6	36	34	173		
1	8	10	44	-1	21	68	-48	42	28	173		
24	-10	38	11	-2	22	-8	28	35	35	173		
2	-80	117	1	10	33	-9	29	34	36	173		
18	100	-97	19	33	10	-10	30	33	37	173		
6	113	4136	-4	-2186	-2005	10	33	32	38	173		
14	-93	-4116	24	2206	2025	33	10	31	39	173		
-4114	30	4229	29	28	27	26	25	35	-142	173		
4184	40	-4159	41	42	43	44	45	-142	35	173		
173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173		

22	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										173
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	35	35	173		
72	22	45	-10	06	-52	-64	84	56	14	173		
-2	16	20	25	2	22	154	-134	34	36	173		
-3	3	10	8	42	23	-7	27	33	37	173		
-4	22	-12	40	13	24	-8	28	32	38	173		
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	31	39	173		
97	160	-164	-10	-11	-12	10	33	30	40	173		
-77	-140	184	30	31	32	33	10	29	41	173		
-2136	-2208	6477	27	26	25	24	-1955	35	-142	173		
2206	2278	-6407	43	44	45	46	2025	-142	35	173		
173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173		

22	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	8	42	173		
13	22	46	-14	06	0	20	30	7	43	173		
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	165	-115	173		
11	5	8	7	40	-1	21	32	6	44	173		
10	21	-14	42	11	-2	22	33	5	45	173		
9	2	20	17	1	10	30	34	4	46	173		
14	18	0	3	19	30	10	29	3	47	173		
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	2	48	173		
-2152	-2156	6438	13	12	11	-1975	9	25	-52	173		
2202	2206	-6388	37	38	39	2025	41	-52	25	173		
173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173		

22	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										173
32	17	35	24	34	33	31	-59	-13	39	173		
40	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	173		
39	11	22	36	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	173		
38	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	173		
37	9	5	8	-3	40	21	30	-16	42	173		
36	12	11	-14	42	11	18	31	-17	43	173		
41	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	173		
-116	50	32	43	33	34	36	35	-19	45	173		
-20	-79	4454	-2180	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	56	173		
46	105	-4428	2206	2025	49	50	51	56	13	173		
173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173		

■ 174th Day of the Year - 23.06.2025

23	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174
-34	21	25	26	27	28	3	29	19	30	174		
37	38	21	20	19	18	43	17	-70	31	174		
-32	78	23	33	-10	06	10	20	7	39	174		
32	14	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	6	40	174		
33	13	1	9	-2	44	9	21	113	-67	174		
34	12	12	-10	39	11	8	22	5	41	174		
35	11	12	-72	109	11	15	7	4	42	174		
36	10	18	102	-79	19	7	15	3	43	174		
-18	81	-2260	4383	-1	-2	-3	-1979	43	-70	174		
51	-104	2306	-4337	47	48	49	2025	44	45	174		
174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174		

23	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										174
28	29	-18	25	26	27	60	-29	-12	38	174		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	65	-13	39	174		
6	24	23	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	174		
17	13	16	20	25	27	10	20	-14	40	174		
18	12	1	9	34	44	9	21	-15	41	174		
19	11	48	-10	39	11	8	22	-16	42	174		
-44	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	174		
33	-7	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	174		
-2280	-2214	6683	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	57	174		
2306	2240	-6657	46	47	48	49	2025	57	13	174		
174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174		

23	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174
23	43	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	39	33	174		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	28	-8	38	34	174		
1	9	8	44	-1	21	66	-46	36	36	174		
22	-10	39	11	-2	22	-8	28	37	35	174		
2	-82	119	1	10	32	-9	29	36	36	174		
18	102	-99	19	32	10	-10	30	35	37	174		
6	112	4237	-4	-2286	-2005	10	32	34	38	174		
14	-92	-4217	24	2306	2025	32	10	33	39	174		
-4210	32	4321	31	30	29	28	27	36	-150	174		
4282	40	-4249	41	42	43	44	45	-150	36	174		
174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174		

23	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										174
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	37	35	174		
71	23	43	-10	06	-51	-68	88	50	22	174		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	158	-138	36	36	174		
-3	3	11	6	42	23	-7	27	35	37	174		
-4	20	-12	41	13	24	-8	28	34	38	174		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	33	39	174		
103	165	-175	-10	-11	-12	10	32	32	40	174		
-83	-145	195	30	31	32	32	10	31	41	174		
-2234	-2308	6673	29	28	27	26	-1953	36	-150	174		
2306	2380	-6601	43	44	45	46	2025	-150	36	174		
174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174		

23	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	10	42	174		
12	23	45	-14	06	0	20	30	9	43	174		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	159	-107	174		
10	5	9	6	40	-1	21	32	8	44	174		
9	20	-14	43	11	-2	22	33	7	45	174		
8	2	19	18	1	10	30	34	6	46	174		
13	18	1	2	19	30	10	29	5	47	174		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	4	48	174		
-2248	-2254	6630	15	14	13	-1973	11	26	-60	174		
2300	2306	-6578	37	38	39	2025	41	-60	26	174		
174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174		

23	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										174
33	19	36	17	35	34	32	-58	-13	39	174		
41	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	174		
40	11	23	35	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	174		
39	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	174		
38	9	5	9	-4	40	21	30	-16	42	174		
37	12	10	-14	43	11	18	31	-17	43	174		
42	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	174		
-122	49	32	51	33	34	36	35	-19	45	174		
-20	-79	4554	-2280	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	57	174		
46	105	-4528	2306	2025	49	50	51	57	13	174		
174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174		

■ 175th Day of the Year - 24.06.2025

24	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										175
-32	17	25	26	27	28	6	29	19	30	175		
37	38	22	21	20	19	41	18	-72	31	175		
-29	76	24	31	-10	06	10	20	8	39	175		
32	15	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	7	40	175		
33	14	1	10	-4	44	9	21	111	-64	175		
34	13	10	-10	40	11	8	22	6	41	175		
35	12	12	-74	111	11	15	6	5	42	175		
36	11	18	104	-81	19	6	15	4	43	175		
-22	85	-2359	4481	0	-1	-2	-1978	43	-72	175		
51	-106	2406	-4434	47	48	49	2025	44	45	175		
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175		

24	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										175
28	29	-18	25	26	27	61	-29	-12	38	175		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	66	-13	39	175		
6	24	24	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	175		
17	13	16	20	25	28	10	20	-14	40	175		
18	12	1	10	34	44	9	21	-15	41	175		
19	11	48	-10	40	11	8	22	-16	42	175		
-43	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	175		
33	-6	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	175		
-2380	-2314	6883	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	58	175		
2406	2340	-6857	46	47	48	49	2025	58	13	175		
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175		

24	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										175
24	43	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	39	33	175		
16	20	25	2	43	-23	28	-8	38	34	175		
1	10	8	44	-1	21	66	-46	36	36	175		
22	-10	40	11	-2	22	-8	28	37	35	175		
2	-82	119	1	10	33	-9	29	36	36	175		
18	102	-99	19	33	10	-10	30	35	37	175		
6	113	4336	-4	-2386	-2005	10	33	34	38	175		
14	-93	-4316	24	2406	2025	33	10	33	39	175		
-4308	32	4419	31	30	29	28	27	36	-149	175		
4380	40	-4347	41	42	43	44	45	-149	36	175		
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175		

24	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										175
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	37	35	175		
72	24	43	-10	06	-52	-66	86	50	22	175		
-2	16	20	25	2	22	156	-136	36	36	175		
-3	3	12	6	42	23	-7	27	35	37	175		
-4	20	-12	42	13	24	-8	28	34	38	175		
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	33	39	175		
101	164	-172	-10	-11	-12	10	33	32	40	175		
-81	-144	192	30	31	32	33	10	31	41	175		
-2334	-2406	6871	29	28	27	26	-1953	36	-149	175		
2406	2478	-6799	43	44	45	46	2025	-149	36	175		
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175		

24	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										175
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	10	42	175		
13	24	44	-14	06	0	20	30	9	43	175		
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	159	-107	175		
11	5	10	5	40	-1	21	32	8	44	175		
10	19	-14	44	11	-2	22	33	7	45	175		
9	2	18	19	1	10	30	34	6	46	175		
14	18	2	1	19	30	10	29	5	47	175		
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	4	48	175		
-2350	-2354	6832	15	14	13	-1973	11	26	-59	175		
2402	2406	-6780	37	38	39	2025	41	-59	26	175		
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175		

24	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										175
34	21	37	10	36	35	33	-57	-13	39	175		
42	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	175		
41	11	24	34	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	175		
40	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	175		
39	9	5	10	-5	40	21	30	-16	42	175		
38	12	9	-14	44	11	18	31	-17	43	175		
43	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	175		
-128	48	32	59	33	34	36	35	-19	45	175		
-20	-79	4654	-2380	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	58	175		
46	105	-4628	2406	2025	49	50	51	58	13	175		
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175		

■ 176th Day of the Year - 25.06.2025

25	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176
-32	18	25	26	27	28	6	29	19	30	176		
37	38	22	21	20	19	41	18	-71	31	176		
-29	76	25	31	-10	06	10	20	8	39	176		
32	15	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	7	40	176		
33	14	1	11	-4	44	9	21	111	-64	176		
34	13	10	-10	41	11	8	22	6	41	176		
35	12	12	-74	111	11	15	7	5	42	176		
36	11	18	104	-81	19	7	15	4	43	176		
-21	84	-2459	4581	0	-1	-2	-1978	43	-71	176		
51	-105	2506	-4534	47	48	49	2025	44	45	176		
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176		

25	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										176
28	29	-18	25	26	27	62	-29	-12	38	176		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	67	-13	39	176		
6	24	25	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	176		
17	13	16	20	25	29	10	20	-14	40	176		
18	12	1	11	34	44	9	21	-15	41	176		
19	11	48	-10	41	11	8	22	-16	42	176		
-42	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	176		
33	-5	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	176		
-2480	-2414	7083	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	59	176		
2506	2440	-7057	46	47	48	49	2025	59	13	176		
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176		

25	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176
25	41	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	41	33	176		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	30	-10	40	34	176		
1	11	6	44	-1	21	64	-44	30	44	176		
20	-10	41	11	-2	22	-8	28	39	35	176		
2	-84	121	1	10	32	-9	29	38	36	176		
18	104	-101	19	32	10	-10	30	37	37	176		
6	112	4437	-4	-2486	-2005	10	32	36	38	176		
14	-92	-4417	24	2506	2025	32	10	35	39	176		
-4404	34	4511	33	32	31	30	29	37	-157	176		
4478	40	-4437	41	42	43	44	45	-157	37	176		
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176		

25	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										176
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	39	35	176		
71	25	41	-10	06	-51	-70	90	44	30	176		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	160	-140	38	36	176		
-3	3	13	4	42	23	-7	27	37	37	176		
-4	18	-12	43	13	24	-8	28	36	38	176		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	35	39	176		
107	169	-183	-10	-11	-12	10	32	34	40	176		
-87	-149	203	30	31	32	32	10	33	41	176		
-2432	-2506	7067	31	30	29	28	-1951	37	-157	176		
2506	2580	-6993	43	44	45	46	2025	-157	37	176		
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176		

25	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	12	42	176		
12	25	43	-14	06	0	20	30	11	43	176		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	153	-99	176		
10	5	11	4	40	-1	21	32	10	44	176		
9	18	-14	45	11	-2	22	33	9	45	176		
8	2	17	20	1	10	30	34	8	46	176		
13	18	3	0	19	30	10	29	7	47	176		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	6	48	176		
-2446	-2452	7024	17	16	15	-1971	13	27	-67	176		
2500	2506	-6970	37	38	39	2025	41	-67	27	176		
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176		

25	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										176
35	23	38	3	37	36	34	-56	-13	39	176		
43	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	176		
42	11	25	33	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	176		
41	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	176		
40	9	5	11	-6	40	21	30	-16	42	176		
39	12	8	-14	45	11	18	31	-17	43	176		
44	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	176		
-134	47	32	67	33	34	36	35	-19	45	176		
-20	-79	4754	-2480	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	59	176		
46	105	-4728	2506	2025	49	50	51	59	13	176		
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176		

■ 177th Day of the Year - 26.06.2025

26	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										177
-30	14	25	26	27	28	9	29	19	30	177		
37	38	23	22	21	20	39	19	-73	31	177		
-26	74	26	29	-10	06	10	20	9	39	177		
32	16	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	8	40	177		
33	15	1	12	-6	44	9	21	109	-61	177		
34	14	8	-10	42	11	8	22	7	41	177		
35	13	12	-76	113	11	15	6	6	42	177		
36	12	18	106	-83	19	6	15	5	43	177		
-25	88	-2558	4679	1	0	-1	-1977	43	-73	177		
51	-107	2606	-4631	47	48	49	2025	44	45	177		
177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177		

26	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										177
28	29	-18	25	26	27	63	-29	-12	38	177		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	68	-13	39	177		
6	24	26	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	177		
17	13	16	20	25	30	10	20	-14	40	177		
18	12	1	12	34	44	9	21	-15	41	177		
19	11	48	-10	42	11	8	22	-16	42	177		
-41	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	177		
33	-4	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	177		
-2580	-2514	7283	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	60	177		
2606	2540	-7257	46	47	48	49	2025	60	13	177		
177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177		

26	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										177
26	41	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	41	33	177		
16	20	25	2	43	-23	30	-10	40	34	177		
1	12	6	44	-1	21	64	-44	30	44	177		
20	-10	42	11	-2	22	-8	28	39	35	177		
2	-84	121	1	10	33	-9	29	38	36	177		
18	104	-101	19	33	10	-10	30	37	37	177		
6	113	4536	-4	-2586	-2005	10	33	36	38	177		
14	-93	-4516	24	2606	2025	33	10	35	39	177		
-4502	34	4609	33	32	31	30	29	37	-156	177		
4576	40	-4535	41	42	43	44	45	-156	37	177		
177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177		

26	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										177
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	39	35	177		
72	26	41	-10	06	-52	-68	88	44	30	177		
-2	16	20	25	2	22	158	-138	38	36	177		
-3	3	14	4	42	23	-7	27	37	37	177		
-4	18	-12	44	13	24	-8	28	36	38	177		
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	35	39	177		
105	168	-180	-10	-11	-12	10	33	34	40	177		
-85	-148	200	30	31	32	33	10	33	41	177		
-2532	-2604	7265	31	30	29	28	-1951	37	-156	177		
2606	2678	-7191	43	44	45	46	2025	-156	37	177		
177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177		

26	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										177
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	12	42	177		
13	26	42	-14	06	0	20	30	11	43	177		
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	153	-99	177		
11	5	12	3	40	-1	21	32	10	44	177		
10	17	-14	46	11	-2	22	33	9	45	177		
9	2	16	21	1	10	30	34	8	46	177		
14	18	4	-1	19	30	10	29	7	47	177		
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	6	48	177		
-2548	-2552	7226	17	16	15	-1971	13	27	-66	177		
2602	2606	-7172	37	38	39	2025	41	-66	27	177		
177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177		

26	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										177
36	25	39	-4	38	37	35	-55	-13	39	177		
44	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	177		
43	11	26	32	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	177		
42	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	177		
41	9	5	12	-7	40	21	30	-16	42	177		
40	12	7	-14	46	11	18	31	-17	43	177		
45	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	177		
-140	46	32	75	33	34	36	35	-19	45	177		
-20	-79	4854	-2580	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	60	177		
46	105	-4828	2606	2025	49	50	51	60	13	177		
177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177		

■ 178th Day of the Year - 27.06.2025

27	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										178
-30	15	25	26	27	28	9	29	19	30	178		
37	38	23	22	21	20	39	19	-72	31	178		
-26	74	27	29	-10	06	10	20	9	39	178		
32	16	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	8	40	178		
33	15	1	13	-6	44	9	21	109	-61	178		
34	14	8	-10	43	11	8	22	7	41	178		
35	13	12	-76	113	11	15	7	6	42	178		
36	12	18	106	-83	19	7	15	5	43	178		
-24	87	-2658	4779	1	0	-1	-1977	43	-72	178		
51	-106	2706	-4731	47	48	49	2025	44	45	178		
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178		

27	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										178
28	29	-18	25	26	27	64	-29	-12	38	178		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	69	-13	39	178		
6	24	27	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	178		
17	13	16	20	25	31	10	20	-14	40	178		
18	12	1	13	34	44	9	21	-15	41	178		
19	11	48	-10	43	11	8	22	-16	42	178		
-40	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	178		
33	-3	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	178		
-2680	-2614	7483	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	61	178		
2706	2640	-7457	46	47	48	49	2025	61	13	178		
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178		

27	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										178
27	39	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	43	33	178		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	32	-12	42	34	178		
1	13	4	44	-1	21	62	-42	24	52	178		
18	-10	43	11	-2	22	-8	28	41	35	178		
2	-86	123	1	10	32	-9	29	40	36	178		
18	106	-103	19	32	10	-10	30	39	37	178		
6	112	4637	-4	-2686	-2005	10	32	38	38	178		
14	-92	-4617	24	2706	2025	32	10	37	39	178		
-4598	36	4701	35	34	33	32	31	38	-164	178		
4674	40	-4625	41	42	43	44	45	-164	38	178		
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178		

27	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										178
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	41	35	178		
71	27	39	-10	06	-51	-72	92	38	38	178		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	162	-142	40	36	178		
-3	3	15	2	42	23	-7	27	39	37	178		
-4	16	-12	45	13	24	-8	28	38	38	178		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	37	39	178		
111	173	-191	-10	-11	-12	10	32	36	40	178		
-91	-153	211	30	31	32	32	10	35	41	178		
-2630	-2704	7461	33	32	31	30	-1949	38	-164	178		
2706	2780	-7385	43	44	45	46	2025	-164	38	178		
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178		

27	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										178
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	14	42	178		
12	27	41	-14	06	0	20	30	13	43	178		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	147	-91	178		
10	5	13	2	40	-1	21	32	12	44	178		
9	16	-14	47	11	-2	22	33	11	45	178		
8	2	15	22	1	10	30	34	10	46	178		
13	18	5	-2	19	30	10	29	9	47	178		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	8	48	178		
-2644	-2650	7418	19	18	17	-1969	15	28	-74	178		
2700	2706	-7362	37	38	39	2025	41	-74	28	178		
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178		

27	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										178
37	27	40	-11	39	38	36	-54	-13	39	178		
45	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	178		
44	11	27	31	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	178		
43	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	178		
42	9	5	13	-8	40	21	30	-16	42	178		
41	12	6	-14	47	11	18	31	-17	43	178		
46	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	178		
-146	45	32	83	33	34	36	35	-19	45	178		
-20	-79	4954	-2680	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	61	178		
46	105	-4928	2706	2025	49	50	51	61	13	178		
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178		

■ 179th Day of the Year - 28.06.2025

28	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179
-28	11	25	26	27	28	12	29	19	30	179	179	
37	38	24	23	22	21	37	20	-74	31	179	179	
-23	72	28	27	-10	06	10	20	10	39	179	179	
32	17	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	9	40	179	179	
33	16	1	14	-8	44	9	21	107	-58	179	179	
34	15	6	-10	44	11	8	22	8	41	179	179	
35	14	12	-78	115	11	15	6	7	42	179	179	
36	13	18	108	-85	19	6	15	6	43	179	179	
-28	91	-2757	4877	2	1	0	-1976	43	-74	179	179	
51	-108	2806	-4828	47	48	49	2025	44	45	179	179	
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	

28	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										179
28	29	-18	25	26	27	65	-29	-12	38	179	179	
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	70	-13	39	179	179	
6	24	28	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	179	179	
17	13	16	20	25	32	10	20	-14	40	179	179	
18	12	1	14	34	44	9	21	-15	41	179	179	
19	11	48	-10	44	11	8	22	-16	42	179	179	
-39	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	179	179	
33	-2	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	179	179	
-2780	-2714	7683	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	62	179	179	
2806	2740	-7657	46	47	48	49	2025	62	13	179	179	
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	

28	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179
28	39	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	43	33	179	179	
16	20	25	2	43	-23	32	-12	42	34	179	179	
1	14	4	44	-1	21	62	-42	24	52	179	179	
18	-10	44	11	-2	22	-8	28	41	35	179	179	
2	-86	123	1	10	33	-9	29	40	36	179	179	
18	106	-103	19	33	10	-10	30	39	37	179	179	
6	113	4736	-4	-2786	-2005	10	33	38	38	179	179	
14	-93	-4716	24	2806	2025	33	10	37	39	179	179	
-4696	36	4799	35	34	33	32	31	38	-163	179	179	
4772	40	-4723	41	42	43	44	45	-163	38	179	179	
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	

28	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										179
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	41	35	179	179	
72	28	39	-10	06	-52	-70	90	38	38	179	179	
-2	16	20	25	2	22	160	-140	40	36	179	179	
-3	3	16	2	42	23	-7	27	39	37	179	179	
-4	16	-12	46	13	24	-8	28	38	38	179	179	
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	37	39	179	179	
109	172	-188	-10	-11	-12	10	33	36	40	179	179	
-89	-152	208	30	31	32	33	10	35	41	179	179	
-2730	-2802	7659	33	32	31	30	-1949	38	-163	179	179	
2806	2878	-7583	43	44	45	46	2025	-163	38	179	179	
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	

28	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	14	42	179		
13	28	40	-14	06	0	20	30	13	43	179		
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	147	-91	179		
11	5	14	1	40	-1	21	32	12	44	179		
10	15	-14	48	11	-2	22	33	11	45	179		
9	2	14	23	1	10	30	34	10	46	179		
14	18	6	-3	19	30	10	29	9	47	179		
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	8	48	179		
-2746	-2750	7620	19	18	17	-1969	15	28	-73	179		
2802	2806	-7564	37	38	39	2025	41	-73	28	179		
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179		

28	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										179
38	29	41	-18	40	39	37	-53	-13	39	179		
46	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	179		
45	11	28	30	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	179		
44	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	179		
43	9	5	14	-9	40	21	30	-16	42	179		
42	12	5	-14	48	11	18	31	-17	43	179		
47	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	179		
-152	44	32	91	33	34	36	35	-19	45	179		
-20	-79	5054	-2780	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	62	179		
46	105	-5028	2806	2025	49	50	51	62	13	179		
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179		

■ 180th Day of the Year - 29.06.2025

29	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180
-28	12	25	26	27	28	12	29	19	30	180		
37	38	24	23	22	21	37	20	-73	31	180		
-23	72	29	27	-10	06	10	20	10	39	180		
32	17	16	20	25	-9	33	-3	9	40	180		
33	16	1	15	-8	44	9	21	107	-58	180		
34	15	6	-10	45	11	8	22	8	41	180		
35	14	12	-78	115	11	15	7	7	42	180		
36	13	18	108	-85	19	7	15	6	43	180		
-27	90	-2857	4977	2	1	0	-1976	43	-73	180		
51	-107	2906	-4928	47	48	49	2025	44	45	180		
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180		

29	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										180
28	29	-18	25	26	27	66	-29	-12	38	180		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	71	-13	39	180		
6	24	29	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	180		
17	13	16	20	25	33	10	20	-14	40	180		
18	12	1	15	34	44	9	21	-15	41	180		
19	11	48	-10	45	11	8	22	-16	42	180		
-38	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	180		
33	-1	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	180		
-2880	-2814	7883	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	63	180		
2906	2840	-7857	46	47	48	49	2025	63	13	180		
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180		

29	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180
29	37	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	45	33	180		
16	20	25	1	43	-23	34	-14	44	34	180		
1	15	2	44	-1	21	60	-40	18	60	180		
16	-10	45	11	-2	22	-8	28	43	35	180		
2	-88	125	1	10	32	-9	29	42	36	180		
18	108	-105	19	32	10	-10	30	41	37	180		
6	112	4837	-4	-2886	-2005	10	32	40	38	180		
14	-92	-4817	24	2906	2025	32	10	39	39	180		
-4792	38	4891	37	36	35	34	33	39	-171	180		
4870	40	-4813	41	42	43	44	45	-171	39	180		
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180		

29	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										180
-19	26	63	-6	-7	25	-6	26	43	35	180		
71	29	37	-10	06	-51	-74	94	32	46	180		
-2	16	20	25	1	22	164	-144	42	36	180		
-3	3	17	0	42	23	-7	27	41	37	180		
-4	14	-12	47	13	24	-8	28	40	38	180		
39	-6	-43	26	27	39	-9	29	39	39	180		
115	177	-199	-10	-11	-12	10	32	38	40	180		
-95	-157	219	30	31	32	32	10	37	41	180		
-2828	-2902	7855	35	34	33	32	-1947	39	-171	180		
2906	2980	-7777	43	44	45	46	2025	-171	39	180		
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180		

29	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180
15	459	18	-323	17	16	14	-94	16	42	180		
12	29	39	-14	06	0	20	30	15	43	180		
11	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	141	-83	180		
10	5	15	0	40	-1	21	32	14	44	180		
9	14	-14	49	11	-2	22	33	13	45	180		
8	2	13	24	1	10	30	34	12	46	180		
13	18	7	-4	19	30	10	29	11	47	180		
44	-417	24	365	25	26	28	27	10	48	180		
-2842	-2848	7812	21	20	19	-1967	17	29	-81	180		
2900	2906	-7754	37	38	39	2025	41	-81	29	180		
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180		

29	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										180
39	31	42	-25	41	40	38	-52	-13	39	180		
47	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	180		
46	11	29	29	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	180		
45	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	180		
44	9	5	15	-10	40	21	30	-16	42	180		
43	12	4	-14	49	11	18	31	-17	43	180		
48	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	180		
-158	43	32	99	33	34	36	35	-19	45	180		
-20	-79	5154	-2880	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	63	180		
46	105	-5128	2906	2025	49	50	51	63	13	180		
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180		

■ 181st Day of the Year - 30.06.2025

30	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										181
-26	8	25	26	27	28	15	29	19	30	181		
37	38	25	24	23	22	35	21	-75	31	181		
-20	70	30	25	-10	06	10	20	11	39	181		
32	18	16	20	25	-10	33	-3	10	40	181		
33	17	1	16	-10	44	9	21	105	-55	181		
34	16	4	-10	46	11	8	22	9	41	181		
35	15	12	-80	117	11	15	6	8	42	181		
36	14	18	110	-87	19	6	15	7	43	181		
-31	94	-2956	5075	3	2	1	-1975	43	-75	181		
51	-109	3006	-5025	47	48	49	2025	44	45	181		
181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181		

30	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										181
28	29	-18	25	26	27	67	-29	-12	38	181		
71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	72	-13	39	181		
6	24	30	69	-10	06	33	-3	209	-183	181		
17	13	16	20	25	34	10	20	-14	40	181		
18	12	1	16	34	44	9	21	-15	41	181		
19	11	48	-10	46	11	8	22	-16	42	181		
-37	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	-17	43	181		
33	0	-33	30	31	32	34	28	-18	44	181		
-2980	-2914	8083	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1999	13	64	181		
3006	2940	-8057	46	47	48	49	2025	64	13	181		
181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181		

30	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										181
30	37	-10	06	0	20	-7	27	45	33	181		
16	20	25	2	43	-23	34	-14	44	34	181		
1	16	2	44	-1	21	60	-40	18	60	181		
16	-10	46	11	-2	22	-8	28	43	35	181		
2	-88	125	1	10	33	-9	29	42	36	181		
18	108	-105	19	33	10	-10	30	41	37	181		
6	113	4936	-4	-2986	-2005	10	33	40	38	181		
14	-93	-4916	24	3006	2025	33	10	39	39	181		
-4890	38	4989	37	36	35	34	33	39	-170	181		
4968	40	-4911	41	42	43	44	45	-170	39	181		
181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181		

30	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/										181
-21	26	66	-6	-7	25	-6	26	43	35	181		
72	30	37	-10	06	-52	-72	92	32	46	181		
-2	16	20	25	2	22	162	-142	42	36	181		
-3	3	18	0	42	23	-7	27	41	37	181		
-4	14	-12	48	13	24	-8	28	40	38	181		
41	-6	-46	26	27	41	-9	29	39	39	181		
113	176	-196	-10	-11	-12	10	33	38	40	181		
-93	-156	216	30	31	32	33	10	37	41	181		
-2928	-3000	8053	35	34	33	32	-1947	39	-170	181		
3006	3078	-7975	43	44	45	46	2025	-170	39	181		
181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181		

30	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									181
16	461	19	-330	18	17	15	-93	16	42	181	
13	30	38	-14	06	0	20	30	15	43	181	
12	12	20	25	3	43	-23	31	141	-83	181	
11	5	16	-1	40	-1	21	32	14	44	181	
10	13	-14	50	11	-2	22	33	13	45	181	
9	2	12	25	1	10	30	34	12	46	181	
14	18	8	-5	19	30	10	29	11	47	181	
38	-418	24	373	25	26	28	27	10	48	181	
-2944	-2948	8014	21	20	19	-1967	17	29	-80	181	
3002	3006	-7956	37	38	39	2025	41	-80	29	181	
181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	

30	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/									181
40	33	43	-32	42	41	39	-51	-13	39	181	
48	6	8	11	70	7	-22	27	-14	40	181	
47	11	30	28	-14	06	19	28	216	-190	181	
46	10	12	20	25	-7	20	29	-15	41	181	
45	9	5	16	-11	40	21	30	-16	42	181	
44	12	3	-14	50	11	18	31	-17	43	181	
49	32	22	19	-40	23	24	26	-18	44	181	
-164	42	32	107	33	34	36	35	-19	45	181	
-20	-79	5254	-2980	-1999	-23	-24	-25	13	64	181	
46	105	-5228	3006	2025	49	50	51	64	13	181	
181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	

4 Author’s Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author’s contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- Inder J. Taneja, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

References

- [1] A. de Winkel, The magic Encyclopedia, <http://home.wanadoo.nl/aaledewinkel/Encyclopedia/index.html>
- [2] C. Boyer, Multimagic Squares and Cubes, <http://www.multimagie.com>
- [3] H. White, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>
- [4] F. Gaspalou, “Magic Squares” <http://www.gaspalou.fr/magic-squares/>

- [5] **W. Trump**, <http://www.trump.de/magic-squares>
- [6] **H. White**, Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/MagicSquares.html>
- [7] **W.S. Andrews**, Magic squares and Cubes, Dover Publications, New York
- [8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order $4k$, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.
- [9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
- [10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.
- [11] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Unequal Sums Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-52, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555260>.
- [12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.
- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.
- [14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Nested Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences, **Zenodo**, June 14, 2019, pp. 1-59, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246586>.
- [15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>.
- [16] **Inder J. Taneja**, General Sum Symmetric and Positive Entries Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, July 04, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3268877>.

- [17] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares With Order Square Magic Sums, **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp. 1-26, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613690>.
- [18] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2020. **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp.1-25. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613698>.
- [19] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2021, **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-33, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4327333>.
- [20] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2022, **Zenodo**, December 28, 2021, pp. 1-38, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807789>
- [21] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>.
- [22] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - II, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-90, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990293>.
- [23] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - III, **Zenodo**, September 01, 2020, pp. 1-93, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011213>.
- [24] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47. **Zenodo**, January 14, 2021, pp. 1-185, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437783>.
- [25] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 7 to 108, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8230214>.
- [26] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6, **Zenodo**, May 23, 2023, pp. 1-23, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7960679>.
- [27] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 13, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-71, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8000467>.

- [28] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 81, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-27, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8231157>.
- [29] **Inder J. Taneja**, Reflexive Year 25: Mathematics of 25 and 2025 in Numbers and Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, December 20, 2024, pp. 1-94, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14533193>.
- [30] **Inder J. Taneja**, Numbers and Magic Squares Representations of Hardy-Ramanujan Number-1729, **Zenodo**, December 20, 2024, pp. 1-127, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14538297>.
- [31] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Orders 3 to 7 Representing Dates and Days of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 04, 2025, pp. 1-474, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15338142>.
- [32] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 8 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 04, 2025, pp. 1-134, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15338246>.
- [33] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 9 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 09, 2025, pp. 1-132, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15375349>.
- [34] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 10 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 21, 2025, pp. 1-59, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15481738>.
-